
D1.3 Ethics and Gender Guidelines

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Cardiovascular Risk Assessment via multimodal data analysis enabling personalised prevention strategies targeting MEnopausal women

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Cardiovascular Risk Assessment via multimodal data analysis enabling personalised prevention strategies targeting MENOPAUSAL women

The CAMEL Consortium consists of:

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6	iBreve Limited	IBREVE	Ireland
7	Magdalena Clinic	MAG	Croatia
8	<i>AE. Megi Health</i>	<i>MEGI</i>	<i>Croatia</i>
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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy AI
CDSS	Clinical Decision Support System
CVD	Cardiovascular Disease
CVD-RA	Cardiovascular Disease Risk Assessment
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DSS	Decision Support System
DVC	Data Version Control
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EEA	European Economic Area
EHDSR	European Health Data Space Regulation
EHR	Electronic Health Record
ERA	European Research Area
ESC	European Society of Cardiology
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GCP	Good Clinical Practice
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEN-AI	Generative AI
GLED	Gender, Legal, Ethics, Data (Committee)
GP	General Practitioner
HDAB	Health Data Access Body
HIC	Human-In-Command
HLEG	High Level Expert Group
IC (F)	Informed Consent (Form)
ID	Intellectual disability
IRB	Institutional Research Board
JCA	Joint Controller Agreement
JREC	Joint Research Ethics Committee

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MDCG	Medical Device Coordination Group
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
OA	Open Access
REAMS	Research Ethics Application Management System
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
PIL/S	Participant Information Leaflet/Sheet
PPI	Public Patient Involvement
PPL	Protection of Privacy Law
PUB	Public
REC	Research Ethics Committee
RF	Risk Factors
SIC	Superintendence of Industry and Commerce
SME	Small to Medium Enterprise
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
SSC	Standard Contractual Clauses
TCA	Total Communication Approach
TCAID	Total Communication Approach for Intellectual Disability

Executive summary

The CAMEL (CARDIOVASCULAR Risk Assessment via multimodal data analysis enabling personalised prevention strategies targeting MENopausal women) project aims to address the urgent clinical need for improved CVD prevention in women, particularly around menopause when the risk significantly increases. The "Ethics and Gender Guidelines" present the legal, ethical, and gender considerations crucial for the project's implementation. This document provides practical guidance to ensure compliance with legal obligations, promote ethical conduct, and integrate best practices in gender and research integrity. The guidelines cover key areas including GDPR, AI Act, Medical Device Regulation, European Health Dataspace Regulation, ethical research frameworks, data management, and gender considerations in research, including addressing sex and gender bias. A Gender, Legal, Ethics, Data (GLED) Committee will monitor and report on relevant issues throughout the project's duration.

The drafting of the Ethics and Gender Guidelines has been coordinated by DCU as Task Leader of Task 1.4 within WP1, devoted to "Legal, privacy and ethics compliance", co-authored by TLX (Legal Guidelines) and TCD (Gender Guidelines), with the contributions from all partners including the members of the Gender, Legal, Ethics and Data (GLED) Committee.

CAMEL's Ethics and Gender Guidelines represent Deliverable 1.3 as described in the Description of the Action (DoA).

The objective of this deliverable is to provide legal, ethical and gender guidelines that will define simple and practical pointers during the implementation of the project, support compliance with underlying legal obligations and promote the adoption of best ethical, gender and research integrity practices. To that end, the structure of the Deliverable is as follows:

- **Section 1. Introduction:** Provides an overview of the CAMEL project's goals, approach to cardiovascular disease risk assessment in menopausal women, and the purpose and audience of this deliverable.
- **Section 2. Legal Principles:** Outlines the key legal frameworks that govern the ethical conduct of research involving human participants, including data protection (GDPR), AI regulations, Medical Device regulations, and the European Health Dataspace Regulation.
- **Section 3. Ethical Principles:** Details the ethical frameworks and principles that CAMEL will adhere to, covering areas such as human participant testing, handling of human cells and tissues, data protection, AI ethics and data management.
- **Section 4. Gender Guidelines:** Provides guidance on integrating sex and gender considerations into the research, and highlights relevant key terms of menopause, sex/gender definitions, intersectionality, bias in research and training.
- **Section 5. Gender, Legal, Ethical and Data Governance:** Describes the governance structure, specifically the GLED Committee, and its role in monitoring and reporting on relevant issues throughout the project.
- **Section 6. Allocation of Resources:** Details the allocation of resources to monitoring and reporting ethical and gender considerations for the project.
- **Section 7. Conclusions:** Summarises the deliverable's key points.

1. Introduction

1.1 CAMEL Concept and Approach

Cardiovascular Disease (CVD) is the leading cause of death in women in the EU, with 17% of women dying from CVD before the age of 65 (European Society of Cardiology-ESC, 2020); while many also present with many non-fatal CVD events at younger ages with life-long consequences. CVD prevention in women in general, and around menopause in particular, when there is a steep rise in risk, is an urgent unmet clinical need. Sex-based differences in clinical presentation, women-specific risk factors, gender bias and many barriers result in misdiagnosis, e.g. dismissing CVD symptoms such as anxiety, or applying less intensive preventive interventions. Existing risk calculators show many limitations in risk assessment. CAMEL will contribute to revert this situation, by the development of a personalised prevention approach based on latest generation AI models for risk stratification complemented with self-assessment and self-management digital tools, to aid in the effective CVD prevention in middle-aged women.

CAMEL project aims to develop a personalised prevention approach based on latest generation AI models for risk stratification, trained on extensive multi-source data, and complemented with self-assessment and self-management digital tools, to aid in the effective CVD prevention in middle-aged women. The first study, CAMEL WOMEN, will use mixed methods (survey, focus groups/interviews and workshops) to examine women’s experience of menopause and cardiovascular disease risk, and their support needs. Figure 1 sums up the CAMEL method for the subsequent three clinical studies, where multiple data sources and participant types will be used to define the CVD-RA (risk assessment) and stratification model.

Figure 1 CAMEL Method

The goal of CAMEL is to develop and validate a novel stratified approach for personalised prevention in women around the menopause transition (40-60 years), enabled by a variety of diagnostic technologies (molecular biomarkers, imaging...), digital data sources (Electronic Health Records (HER), cohorts, registries, biobanks...) and participant groups (women aged 40-60 years, healthcare professionals, ...).

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CAMEL will investigate different approaches for data integration and computational modelling, developing state-of-the-art approaches in AI and personalised risk prediction. The most successful data sources and CVD-RA models will be integrated into a novel stratified personalised prevention model adapted to different risk levels and primary and secondary prevention scenarios while considering existing evidence and women-specific risks and needs. It will be complemented by a preventive smart mobile health intervention with a self-awareness, self-assessment and self-management strategy for reducing individual CVD risks, incorporating evidence-based clinical interventions and psychological and community-based support.

1.2 CAMEL Clinical Studies

Ethical approval will be required from each of the six CAMEL clinical sites for each of the CAMEL clinical studies. The CAMEL WOMEN study will also require ethical approval from the Trinity College Ethics Committee.

Short name	Full name	Study type	WPs
STUDY 1: CAMEL- WOMEN	Study 1: CAMEL-WOMEN. Women's experience of menopause and CVD & support needs	Mixed methods (survey, focus groups/interview, workshops)	4
STUDY 2: CAMEL- RS	Study 2: CAMEL-RS. Retrospective Study for EHR-based incident prediction modelling and temporal disease trajectory analysis	Retrospective/ Observational	5,6
STUDY 3: CAMEL- OS	Study 3: CAMEL-OS. Prospective Observational Study for women CVD-RA modelling and stratification with multiple data sources.	Prospective/ Observational	7, 11-12
STUDY 4: CAMEL- IS	Study 4: CAMEL-IS. Prospective Interventional study for wom en CVD monitoring and self-management	Prospective/ Interventional	8, 13

Table 1 CAMEL Clinical Studies

1.3 Purpose of this Deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide comprehensive Ethics and Gender Guidelines for the CAMEL project, defining the legal, ethical and gender procedures and principles CAMEL researchers need to follow to ensure ethical, safe and unbiased involvement of participant involvement in all stages of the project.

This Deliverable is defined in compliance with the obligations established in Article 14 of CAMEL Grant Agreement, “Ethics and Values” and in Article 11, “Proper Implementation of the Action” (legal) and Article 15, “Data Protection”.

CAMEL’s Ethics and Gender Guidelines (D1.3) provides legal, ethical and gender guidelines to ensure the project complies with legal obligations, adopts best ethical and research integrity practices, and addresses gender considerations in its work on cardiovascular risk assessment in menopausal women. The scope of this deliverable is to explain the international and national legal environment within which CAMEL is operating, with particular emphasis on conduct within and between EU and Non-EU countries; the institutional policies and practices of CAMEL partners and the guidelines that they will follow for the conduct of ethical research; and procedures to manage relevant gender and sex issues. Finally, governance processes that will monitor and ensure adherence to these frameworks and guidelines will be described.

The drafting of the Ethics and Gender Guidelines has been coordinated by DCU as Task Leader of Task 1.4 within WP1, devoted to “Legal, privacy and ethics compliance” with the contributions from all partners, including TCD (gender guidelines), TLX (legal guidelines) and the remaining members of the Gender, Legal, Ethics and Data (GLED) Committee (VICOM, Clinical sites). To that end, the Guide has followed the guidelines provided by Horizon Europe for ethical management of research projects ([Retrieved 10.01.2025](#)), ensuring the compliance of CAMEL with the ethical and gender management requirements under Article 14 of the Grant Agreement.

CAMEL’s Ethics and Gender Guidelines represent Deliverable 1.3 as described in the Description of the Action (DoA). It should be noted that this represents ethics and gender guidelines as they are understood at the outset of the CAMEL project. Ethics and gender issues will be monitored across the duration of the project by the GLED Committee and any amendments to these guidelines will be captured, updated and circulated to the project team as required. Details of these issues and resulting solutions and changes to the guidelines will be reported in the Management Reports (Deliverables D2.1 due in Month 36 and D3.1 due in Month 60).

1.4 Intended Audience

The intended audience of this deliverable are the CAMEL consortium partners, as it describes all processes related to the ethics and gender management of the project. It is also intended for the EC services, since this document describes CAMEL ethics and gender guidelines in compliance with Article 14 of the Grant Agreement. Following the agreed Description of Action, D1.3 is available for Public (PUB) access. The Deliverable will be disseminated once approved by the EC in CAMEL’s project website and Zenodo community.

2. Legal Principles

The CARAMEL project is a complex research project. Consequently, legal requirements in multiple domains apply. This section explains the requirements in **data protection law**, **artificial intelligence** and **medical devices regulation**. It also looks at the **European Health Data Space Regulation**, which was recently adopted by the Council, and which will come into force in the coming months.

2.1 GDPR / Protection of Personal Data

The **General Data Protection Regulation**¹ or **GDPR** sets out the requirements for fair and lawful processing of personal data in the EU. The GDPR applies to all ‘processing of personal data’ in the project, a term that is broadly defined: ‘**personal data**’ is any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person, directly or indirectly including by identifiers, while ‘**processing**’ is any operation performed on personal data, including access or storage.²

This means that the GDPR will set requirements for nearly all uses of personal data within the project, such as processing any non-anonymised data relating to (theoretically) identifiable persons, training AI on personal data, using AI to make decisions about individuals, processing health data (which is a special category of personal data) or ancillary activities of the project involving personal data, like communication and dissemination activities.

Processing under the GDPR requires compliance with seven **key principles**. The table below provides an overview of these principles.

GDPR principle	Explanation
Lawfulness	Any processing of personal data must comply with all applicable laws and must have a legal basis. Specific requirements apply for sensitive personal data, including health data: its processing is prohibited unless an exception applies (including explicit consent or scientific research exception).
Purpose limitation	The purpose of the processing should be specific, explicit, and legitimate, and any further processing of the personal data should be compatible with that original purpose.
Transparency	Data subjects should be clearly informed of the processing of their personal data and of potential risks. They should also be informed of their data subject rights and how they can exercise those. Partners in

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

² Article 4 GDPR.

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	the project should provide all this information prior to the commencement of the data processing.
Fairness	Personal data should not be processed in a way that is unjustifiably detrimental, unlawfully discriminatory, unexpected or misleading to the data subject.
Data minimisation	Only personal data that is adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the purposes should be processed. This principle is closely linked to the implementation of appropriate safeguards for the rights and freedoms of the data subject, such as pseudonymisation and anonymisation.
Storage limitation	Personal data shall only be kept for as long as necessary for the purposes of processing, and then erased or anonymised, unless there are legitimate reasons for further retention.
Integrity and confidentiality	Processing must ensure appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using technical or organizational measures appropriate to the level of risk involved. This implies assessing the level of risk involved in the processing and is linked to the requirement in certain cases to conduct a data protection impact assessment .
Accountability	Controllers must take responsibility for and demonstrate compliance with the other six principles discussed above. Whenever controllers jointly determine the means and purposes of the processing, they are also jointly responsible for compliance. Controllers are also accountable for any processing performed on their behalf by service providers, the so-called data processors .

Table 2 GDPR key principles

The key principles for personal data processing and essential GDPR requirements are further examined in this chapter.

2.1.1 Legal basis and purpose of processing

The requirements for partners processing personal data within the project are primarily based on the principles of lawfulness and purpose limitation.

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Lawfulness:³ any processing of personal data must comply with all applicable laws and must have a legal basis.⁴ Specific requirements apply for sensitive personal data, including health data: its processing is prohibited unless an exception applies.⁵

- The project partners are always required to have a **legal basis** for processing data in the project. For health data (or other sensitive personal data) they must also be able to rely on one of those exceptions. So, if they're processing sensitive data, partners need a legal basis (listed in Article 6(1)) and an exception for that data (listed in Article 9(2)).⁶ The relevant exceptions for the project are explicit consent⁷ and scientific research⁸.
- **Explicit consent** – Partners in the project must obtain consent from participants in the prospective research study before processing their data. This consent must be free, specific, informed, unambiguous and explicit (so, given in an express statement of consent). While consent must be specific, the GDPR does allow for some flexibility for a scientific research project when the specific purposes of data processing cannot be determined at the time of data collection.⁹ Where partners are getting access to retrospective data and submitting it to the project, they must assess whether the original informed consent provided by the patients covers the scientific research activities to be undertaken in the project, or whether other legal grounds for secondary use of data for scientific research purposes apply. We also note that data subjects can withdraw their consent at any point.
- **Scientific research** – Partners can rely on this exception, for example for certain retrospective sensitive personal data, but only if the processing complies with the following conditions: it is necessary for scientific research purposes based on Union or Member State law, it complies with Article 89(1) of the GDPR, it is proportionate to the aim pursued, it respects the essence of the right to data protection and it provides for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject. The partners could use this exception in conjunction with a legal basis such as Article 6(1)(e) or (f) GDPR, and relevant national regulations, if applicable.¹⁰ It must be highlighted that this lawful basis only applies if appropriate safeguards are in place, for example pseudonymising the data if anonymising is not possible. Member States can determine what such “appropriate safeguards” are (see section 2.1.5 below on national data protection requirements below).

3 Article 5(1)(a) GDPR.

4 Article 6(1) GDPR lists the possible legal bases: either the data subject's specific consent, or the processing is necessary to perform a contract, to comply with a legal obligation, to protect vital interests of a natural person, to perform a task in the public interest or the legitimate interest that are not overridden by the interests of the data subject.

5 Article 9 GDPR.

6 Recital 51 GDPR.

7 Article 9(2)(a) GDPR.

8 Article 9(2)(j) GDPR.

9 Recital 33 GDPR: consent can be a valid legal basis in such cases, even if it is only described in a general manner, such as in terms of research questions or fields of research to be explored.

10 See the Article 29 Working Party Guidelines on consent under the GDPR: “The GDPR does not restrict the application of Article 6 to consent alone, with regard to processing data for research purposes. As long as appropriate safeguards are in place, such as the requirements under Article 89(1), and the processing is fair, lawful, transparent and accords with data minimisation standards and individual rights, other lawful bases such as Article 6(1)(e) or (f) may be available. This also applies to special categories of data pursuant to the derogation of Article 9(2)(j)”, European Data Protection Board Guidelines 05/2020 on Consent under the GDPR, p. 30, https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/file1/edpb_guidelines_202005_consent_en.pdf.

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- Ultimately, it is the responsibility of the partner collecting, accessing or providing the data to ensure that this is done lawfully and that a legal basis is established for the processing of the data. The specific conditions for establishing such legal basis may differ depending on the national law and the context in which the data is collected.

Purpose limitation:¹¹ *the purpose of the processing should be specific, explicit, and legitimate, and further processing of the personal data should be compatible with that original purpose.*

- When partners collect prospective data of patients for the project, they should use the **patient information sheet** to explicitly communicate the purposes of processing to the data subjects beforehand, including the relevant safeguards being implemented to reduce and mitigate risks.
- Processing personal data for a new purpose requires explicit consent from the data subject or compatibility¹² of the new purpose with the original purpose for which the data was collected. In the case of scientific research however, Article 5 of the GDPR presumes that the **re-use of personal data for research purposes** is compatible with the original purpose if appropriate safeguards are implemented according to Article 89 of the GDPR and national data protection rules are complied with. These national requirements typically require the approval of an ethics committee and the provision of a guarantee of appropriate safeguards (like pseudonymisation, data minimisation, encryption, anonymisation where possible, etc.) (see section 2.1.5 below on national data protection requirements).
- When the partners repurpose retrospective health data (including pseudonymised data) for the project, they must assess whether:
 1. The scientific research activities intended in the project are covered under the original informed consent form signed by the patients, or
 2. It is feasible to obtain new consent from the patients, or
 3. The secondary use of health data is permissible. This includes verifying national regulations, ensuring compliance with national exemptions to consent for research purposes (including approval from the relevant ethics committee, if applicable), and confirming that appropriate technical and organisational safeguards are in place for handling patient data.

2.1.2 Data subject rights

Data subjects have various rights under the GDPR, as outlined in Chapter 3. These rights impose requirements on the partners, which are discussed here alongside the requirements derived from the principles of transparency, fairness, and accuracy.

¹¹ Article 5(1)(b) GDPR.

¹² Article 6(4) of the GDPR outlines the factors controllers must consider when assessing the compatibility of secondary use, including: the link between the original and new purposes of processing, the context of personal data collection keeping in mind the relationship between the data subjects and the controller, the nature of the personal data, the potential consequences of the intended further processing for data subjects, the implementation of appropriate safeguards

Transparency and fairness:¹³ *data subjects should be clearly informed about the processing of their personal data, including potential risks, while ensuring that adverse effects on them are avoided.*

- The transparency requirement is further elaborated through **information rights**:¹⁴ the data subjects must be informed of the controller's identity, the purpose of the processing, the categories of data being processed, the storage period, associated risks and safeguards, and their data subject rights. This information must be provided in a clear, concise, transparent, and easily understandable manner, considering the reasonable expectations of the data subject.¹⁵ Additionally, if a decision that significantly impacts data subjects is based solely on automated processing, controllers must inform them about the automated decision-making process, including the model's underlying logic, anticipated impacts, and significance. Partners in the project must provide this information to data subjects before data processing through various channels, such as the patient information sheet for the prospective study or the privacy policy on the website.
- The requirement of fairness is particularly important when **AI technology** is used.¹⁶ Partners should implement specific safeguards to prevent adverse effects for data subjects, including ensuring that the training data is not biased or discriminatory. They should also consider the potential for errors in the AI systems during development, regularly assess how these errors may impact decisions made based on their output and implement measures to mitigate and reduce risks.

Accuracy:¹⁷ *personal data shall be accurate and up to date; otherwise, it should be erased or rectified.*

- Partners contributing data to the project must ensure that the data is of representative quality and accurately annotated. Therefore, standards and guidelines for both data submission and quality control are necessary. Partners should also have a procedure for correcting or removing inaccurate data (including pseudonymised data), particularly upon legitimate request of the data subject, unless exemptions apply.

Data subject rights and their exercise

Data subjects have specific rights regarding the processing of their personal data under the GDPR. These rights enable data subjects to exercise control over their personal data, obtain information about the processing, and, in some cases, influence such processing. These rights include the right to:¹⁸

- Obtain **information** about the processing of their personal data,
- Obtain **access** to and a copy of their personal data,
- Request **correction** of incorrect, inaccurate or incomplete personal data,
- Request **erasure** of personal data when it is no longer needed or if processing it is unlawful,

¹³ Article 5(1)(a) GDPR.

¹⁴ See Articles 12-14 GDPR for the conditions and the full list of information to be provided.

¹⁵ Article 29 Working Party Guidelines on Transparency under the GDPR of 11 April 2018, § 26-27, <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/items/622227/en>.

¹⁶ Recital 71 GDPR.

¹⁷ Article 5(1)(d) GDPR.

¹⁸ Articles 15-22 GDPR.

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- Request the **restriction** of processing of their personal data in specific cases,
- **Receive** their personal data in a machine-readable format and have it transferred to another controller,
- **Object** to the processing of personal data for marketing purposes or on grounds relating to the particular situation of the concerned data subject,
- Request that decisions based on **automated processing**, concerning the data subject or significantly affecting the data subject, are made by natural persons, and not solely by automated means (computers). Data subjects also have the right in this case to express their point of view and to contest the decision.

Each partner processing personal data must allow the data subjects to **exercise their rights**. For personal data where the partners are joint controllers, they must follow the provisions for handling data subject requests as outlined in the joint controllership arrangement.

However, it is important to note that the rights described above cannot always be exercised as absolute rights, and certain restrictions might apply. Specifically, in the case of a health research project such as CAMEL, national law may include **derogations and limitations** to some of these data subject rights. The GDPR provides for possible restrictions on data subject rights in the interest of public health or the protection of data subjects or the rights or freedoms of others.¹⁹ Furthermore, the data subjects' rights of access, rectification, restriction and objection may be limited in the interest of scientific research purposes, insofar as these rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes. The derogations must be necessary to achieve those purposes, and safeguards, as outlined in Article 89(1) GDPR, must be implemented.²⁰

Partners must therefore, also assess the applicability of any national derogations to data subject rights when responding to data subject requests. Many Member States significantly restrict certain rights in the context of scientific research (see the section on national data protection requirements below).

Additionally, in the case of **aggregated data**, partners may not or no longer be able to identify the data subject submitting a request. In such case, the data subject rights cannot be exercised unless the data subject provides additional information to allow identification.²¹

Finally, it is important to note that patients might have **additional rights** under national patient laws, such as access to their medical records or the correction of errors. Partners should be aware of these rights as well.

2.1.3 Appropriate safeguards

The principles of data minimisation, integrity and confidentiality, as well as the processing of health data in certain circumstances (see the principles of lawfulness and purpose limitation described above), require partners to implement safeguards in order to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subjects. Specifically, they must implement **technical and organisational measures** that are appropriate to the risks associated with data processing. This section also addresses the principle of storage limitation, the performance of data

¹⁹ Article 23(1) GDPR provides that Union or Member State law may restrict by way of legislative measure the scope of the data subjects' rights in certain circumstances.

²⁰ Article 89(2) GDPR.

²¹ Article 11(2) GDPR.

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protection impact assessments, and the safeguards to be implemented in the case of data transfers to non-EEA countries within the project.

Data minimisation:²² *Only personal data that is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary for the purposes should be processed.*

- Implementing data minimisation in a research project is closely linked to the appropriate safeguards required by Article 89(1) of the GDPR to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subjects involved. Partners should limit the processing of personal data to the minimum necessary to achieve the research objectives and document the reasons for the extent of data used. Access to data in the project database will also be restricted. The partners also plan to employ several protective measures and safeguards to ensure data minimization and the protection of data subjects' rights.
- **Pseudonymisation** – Pseudonymising data means²³ making the data no longer attributable to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, which is kept separately and is subjected to appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure that the data cannot be linked to that data subject. Pseudonymisation reduces the overall risks arising from personal data processing. Partners will notably collect prospective data in the research study in a coded manner: each patient will receive an identification code that does not include any data allowing personal identification. Only the principal investigator will have a separate list linking the identification codes of the patients with their clinical and personal data, and this document will not be accessible to anyone else except in cases where the law mandates access by health authorities.
- **Anonymisation** – Anonymising data means²⁴ irreversibly transforming personal data so that it can no longer be attributed to an identifiable person by any means likely to be used. Anonymisation is mandatory when it does not hinder the intended purpose of processing. Anonymised data no longer relate to an identifiable person and thus falls outside the scope of the GDPR. While anonymisation in the sense of the GDPR is a high threshold,²⁵ it must be assessed from the perspective of the data recipient. Only if the recipient does not have the legal or technical means to reidentify the individual, can the transmitted data be considered anonymised.²⁶ Some of the retrospective data sources the partners will use within the project are anonymised (aggregated data), meaning the GDPR does not apply to the processing of that data. Moreover, partners may also rely on anonymisation to comply with the FAIR principles (making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) during and after the project.

22 Article 5(1)(c) GDPR; see also the glossary section for 'data minimisation' of the European Data Protection Supervisor, https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/data-protection/glossary/d_en.

23 Article 4(5) GDPR.

24 Recital 26 of the GDPR states that in order "to determine whether a natural person is identifiable, account should be taken of all the means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out, either by the controller or by another person to identify the natural person directly or indirectly. To ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used to identify the natural person, account should be taken of all objective factors, such as the costs and the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and technological developments."

25 This is mainly because of the fact that one must look at "all means reasonably likely to be used either by the controller or by another person to re-identify the data subject". The EU Court of Justice has also clarified that "it is not required that all the information enabling the identification of the data subject must be in the hands of one person", C-582/14, Breyer, § 43. Only where re-identification is prohibited by law or practically impossible in terms of a disproportionate effort concerning time, cost and manpower one could argue that the data is to be considered anonymous, C-582/14, Breyer, §45-46.

26 EU General Court, T-557/20, SRB v. EDPS, §97 and 105.

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- **Federated Learning** – Unlike conventional centralized machine learning methods, federated learning does not require transmission of all training data from multiple devices to a central repository for model training.²⁷ Local training of the model on the device where the data initially resides can help preserve the privacy of the data.²⁸ The partners in the project might consider using a federated learning approach when training AI algorithms on retrospective clinical data if these data are to remain at the clinical sites.

Storage limitation:²⁹ *Personal data shall only be kept for as long as necessary for the purposes of processing and then erased or anonymised, unless there are legitimate reasons for further retention.*

- Partners must define **retention periods** for the personal (pseudonymised) data used for the project and clearly inform data subjects (including research participants) of this storage duration. This will ensure that the data is not kept for periods longer than necessary and is deleted or anonymised thereafter.
- The GDPR does allow for the possibility of storing personal data for extended periods of time – however, not indefinitely – provided it is processed solely for **scientific research purposes** and that appropriate technical and organisational measures, in accordance with Article 89(1), are implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects.

Integrity and confidentiality:³⁰ *Processing must ensure appropriate security of personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing, as well as against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using technical or organizational measures appropriate to the level of risk involved.*

- Partners should implement **measures in their information systems** used for the project that enhance data protection and manage data access through identity and access management protocols. The exact measures will depend on the state of the art of technologies, the implementation costs, and the scope, context and purposes of data processing (through an assessment of risks to the rights and freedoms of individuals).³¹ These measures can include pseudonymisation, anonymisation and encryption, ensuring the continuous confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services. Additionally, measures should be in place to restore personal data access and availability in a timely manner following a technical or physical incident, and the partners should regularly test, assess, and evaluate the effectiveness of technical and organizational measures to ensure security of the processing.³²

Data protection impact assessment

The appropriateness of all the safeguards and measures mentioned above depends on the risks that the data processing poses to the data subjects' rights and freedoms. Therefore, partners should assess those risks. The GDPR requires a formal data protection impact

²⁷ European Data Protection Supervisor, Publication on Federated Learning, https://edps.europa.eu/press-publications/publications/techsonar/federated-learning_en.

²⁸ ENISA, Securing Machine Learning Algorithms, December 2021, <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/securing-machine-learning-algorithms>.

²⁹ Article 5(1)(e) GDPR.

³⁰ Articles 5(1)(f) and 32 GDPR.

³¹ Article 25(1) GDPR.

³² Article 32(1) GDPR.

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assessment (DPIA) prior to processing any personal data, which may result in **high risks to the rights and freedoms of individuals**, particularly in cases where new technologies are used.³³ Given the processing of large volumes of health data and the use of AI tools in the context of the project, a DPIA will indeed be required.³⁴

Partners must thus conduct a DPIA, or several DPIAs for the different components of the project. They should first assess whether the intended processing operations are necessary and proportionate for their purposes. Next, they should identify the risks posed by the processing activities in various domains, such as legal and ethical compliance risks, security risks or risks associated with the re-identification of individuals. Once these risks are identified, partners should evaluate what specific measures can be implemented to mitigate them effectively.

Additionally, if the processing may result in high risk, the controller is required to consult with the supervisory authority, which may provide negative advice regarding the processing, depending on the mitigating measures proposed by the controller³⁵.

All of the measures that partners plan to implement, as mentioned above and in their joint controllership arrangement, may constitute appropriate safeguards and mitigating measures depending on the conclusions of the DPIA.

International Data transfers

Transfers from the EEA to a third country

The GDPR contains specific requirements for any **transfer of personal data to countries outside the European Economic Area (EEA)**.³⁶ The project includes partners from outside the EEA, specifically **Colombia** and **Israel**. During the course of the project, non-EEA partners may be granted access to certain personal data under certain circumstances. If this occurs, appropriate safeguards will be implemented.

For Israel, the European Commission has declared that this country provides an adequate level of protection for personal data.³⁷ A data transfer to partners in Israel is therefore permissible based on this **adequacy decision**.

No such adequacy decision has been issued for Colombia. Any transfer to the Colombian partner in the consortium must be assessed beforehand (via a data transfer impact assessment) and accompanied by appropriate safeguards. One of such safeguards are **Standard Contractual Clauses (SSC)** – pre-approved legal contracts issued by the European Commission – that allow the transfer of personal data from the EEA to non-EEA countries. They ensure that the recipient provides a level of protection equivalent to GDPR standards.

³³ Article 35 GDPR.

³⁴ See also Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of the GDPR, <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/items/611236/en>, and the lists of national data protection authorities, for the assessment whether DPIAs are required.

³⁵ Article 36.1 of the GDPR

³⁶ Chapter V of the GDPR, Articles 44-46.

³⁷ Commission Decision of 31 January 2011 pursuant to Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the adequate protection of personal data by the State of Israel with regard to automated processing of personal data. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32011D0061>.

After the Schrems II ruling, organizations using SCC must assess the risk of data transfers via TIA (Transfer Impact Assessment) and implement supplementary measures such as end-to-end encryption, anonymisation or pseudonymisation, transparency reports etc.

Transfers from a third country into the EEA

Certain categories of data will be imported from Colombia and Israel to the partners located in the EEA. Specifically, these will be:

- EHR data from Israel and Colombia used for the Retrospective Studies within WP5,
- Blood samples, questionnaire and wearable data from Colombia, during the Observational (WP11-12) and Interventional (WP13) Studies.

Such transfers will be conducted in compliance with the relevant laws and regulations of Colombia³⁸ and Israel.

For more details please refer to sections 2.5 below (“Non-European Countries”) as well as section 7.4 of the D1.2 “Data Management Plan” (page 54).

2.1.4 Controllers and accountability

Lastly, the proper identification of controllers and processors is critical for compliance with data protection laws and for enabling data subjects to exercise their rights. This is also in line with the principle of accountability.

Accountability:³⁹ *Controllers must take responsibility for and demonstrate compliance with all other key GDPR principles.*

- It is not enough to merely comply with the requirements and obligations set out in the GDPR; compliance must also be demonstrated. Partners should **document** measures taken to achieve compliance with the principles of data processing, ensuring they can be readily shared with data subjects and supervisory authorities upon request.

Joint controllership and processors

A controller determines the purpose and means – i.e. the “why” and “how” of data processing.⁴⁰ When two or more entities **jointly determine the means and purposes of processing**, they are considered joint controllers.

Within the project, all consortium partners will be regarded as joint controllers for personal data processing occurring in the project’s context. This classification arises from their shared decision-making authority over both the purposes and means of processing. However, each partner will remain an independent controller for any additional processing carried out for their specific purposes beyond the project’s scope. Under the GDPR, joint controllers must clearly and transparently define their respective responsibilities for ensuring compliance with GDPR obligations. While the regulation does not prescribe a specific legal form for such arrangements, the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) advises establishing a binding document, such as a contract or other legally enforceable agreement under EU or Member State law. To ensure legal certainty, transparency, and accountability, the consortium will

³⁸ Colombia: Habeas Data Law Decree 1581 of 2012 and Decree 1377 of 2013. Israel: Privacy Protection Law, 1981 (PPL) and its associated regulations.

³⁹ Article 5(2) GDPR.

⁴⁰ Article 4(7) GDPR.

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develop a Joint Controllership Agreement (JCA) outlining the roles, duties, and relationships of joint controllers concerning data subjects (patients). The key elements of this agreement will be made available to data subjects, such as in the project's information sheet or on the project website, ensuring clarity on how their data is handled. Furthermore, all partners must formally sign the JCA before any data processing or sharing begins.

When partners enlist the services of an external provider or subcontractor to process personal data on their behalf, this third party qualifies as a “**processor**” under the GDPR.⁴¹ In this case, the partner enlisting this external provider should first ensure that the provider can be entrusted with the delegated processing activities. This means the processor must provide adequate guarantees to implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to protect the data subject's rights and meet GDPR requirements. If this is the case, the partner can engage the processor and should conclude a **data processing agreement** with this provider.

2.1.5 National data protection requirements

As mentioned above, the GDPR allows Member States to determine certain data protection requirements, particularly in the areas of **health and research**. Partners from **Spain, Croatia, Greece** and **Lithuania** will provide clinical data during the research studies; therefore, they should be aware of all relevant requirements under their national laws. Some common requirements under various national laws are as follows:

- **Appropriate safeguards** – Member States may determine what constitutes the appropriate safeguards under Article 89(1) GDPR for scientific research within their countries. National legislation generally includes four types of requirements: **anonymisation or pseudonymisation, informed consent, prior approval or authorisation** (e.g. from a research ethics committee or an information security committee), and/or **data residency**.
- **Data subject rights** – Article 89(2) GDPR allows Member States to impose restrictions of the data subject rights to access, rectification, erasure, objection and restriction when processing data for scientific purposes. In the healthcare context, patients may not always be able to fully exercise their right to access (since the patient's medical record may also contain a medical professional's work, with certain parts possibly needing to be shielded from the patient to protect their wellbeing) or their rectification or erasure (since the patient's medical record must remain complete).
- **Access to electronic health records** – Most Member States have stricter data-sharing requirements for data from patients' medical records. As a general rule, any additional use of the data in the medical record is only allowed with the patient's consent. However, several exceptions exist where patient consent is not required to access or share the data. Public health and research purposes are usually exceptions, provided that requirements such as anonymisation or pseudonymisation of the data are met, as described above.

2.2 AI Act / Trustworthy AI

⁴¹ Article 4(8) GDPR; See European Data Protection Board, Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR, https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2023-10/EDPB_guidelines_202007_controllerprocessor_final_en.pdf for detailed guidance on the qualification of processors.

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The artificial intelligence models developed within the project, especially in its later stages, must comply with all applicable requirements of the EU’s **Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act)**.⁴² The AI Act entered into force on 1 August 2024 and most of its provisions will start applying from 2 August 2026.

The AI Act applies to “**AI systems**”, that is machine-based systems that:

- are designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy,
- may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment, and
- for explicit or implicit objectives, infer from received input how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments.

The requirements that the AI Act imposes on an AI system depend on the level of risk associated with that system. Systems with a higher risk are subject to more stringent requirements.

2.2.1 Classification of high-risk AI systems

A system will be classified as a ‘high-risk AI system’ if it meets one of the following two criteria:

<p>The AI system is (incorporated in) a regulated product</p>	<p>This criterion covers AI systems that are products regulated by the EU harmonisation legislation (enumerated in Annex I to the AI Act), which need to undergo a third-party conformity assessment. It also covers AI systems that are intended to be used as a safety component of such products.</p> <p>Importantly, the said Annex I to the AI Act includes the MDR (Medical Device Regulation). Any medical device software intended for diagnosis, therapeutic purposes or monitoring physiological processes is classified as Class II a medical device under the MDR and requires a conformity assessment to be conducted by a notified body. Therefore, any AI system that qualifies as Class II a medical device software will automatically be considered a high-risk AI system.</p>
<p>The AI system performs a task in a high risk area</p>	<p>AI systems not subject to existing product regulation can still be classified as high-risk if they perform tasks in specific use cases or application domains. These tasks are defined in Annex III to the AI Act, and include areas such as biometrics, critical infrastructure, education, employment, essential public services or law enforcement. Article 6 of the AI Act also specifies exceptions to this classification.</p>

Table 3 Criteria for classification as high-risk AI system

⁴² Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>.

2.2.2 Requirements for high-risk AI systems

The requirements that apply to high-risk AI systems are detailed in Chapter III, Section 2 of the AI Act. Key requirements include:

- a risk management system,
- the quality and relevance of datasets used,
- technical documentation and record-keeping,
- transparency and the provision of information to deployers,
- human oversight, and
- robustness, accuracy and cybersecurity.

Article 10 of the AI Act lays down specific requirements for **data and data governance**. The training, validation and testing datasets used for the high-risk AI model must meet the quality criteria set by the AI Act. Some key requirements are that the datasets are:

- subject to data governance and management practices,
- relevant, sufficiently representative, and to the best extent possible, free of errors and complete in view of the intended purpose, and
- take into account the specific geographical, contextual, behavioural or functional setting in which the system is intended to be used.

Providers of high-risk AI systems cannot place such systems on the EU market before they have undergone a **conformity assessment** in accordance with 43 of the AI Act. Once the conformity assessment is concluded and the system complies with all of the AI Act requirements, a declaration of conformity will be signed. The AI system should then bear a CE marking and can be placed on the market.

It shall be noted, that when a third-party conformity assessment is required by Union harmonization legislation, such as the MDR, the notified bodies designated under that legislation, are entitled to assess the AI system's conformity with AI Act requirements. This means that a single conformity assessment covering both the MDR and the AI Act can be conducted.

2.2.3 AI Act and scientific research exceptions

For most of the project, the AI systems will be developed and trained for research purposes.

The AI Act does not apply to AI systems or models, including their output, that are specifically developed and put into service for the sole purpose of **scientific research and development** (Recital 25 of the AI Act). Moreover, the regulation does not apply to any research, testing or development activity regarding the AI systems or models, before they are placed on the market or put into service. However, it does apply to **testing in real-world conditions**. Therefore, so long as the AI models developed within the CAMEL project have no impact on patient treatment or decision-making, this will not constitute real-world deployment under the AI Act. However, if interventional studies later on, involve AI-driven clinical decision support (in other words: the AI is tested in interventional study where it influences clinical care), this would likely qualify as high-risk AI under the AI Act.

In any case, and considering the objectives of the project, outlined in the CAMEL grant agreement - namely for the cardiovascular disease risk assessment, clinical decision support system, and stratification scheme based on the AI models to be used in clinical practice and

perhaps commercialized – the partners should consider all relevant requirements of the AI Act for high-risk AI systems when developing and testing AI models.

2.3 Medical Device Regulation

Regulations on medical devices will be relevant to two aspects of the project. First, medical devices developed by project partners will be used during the prospective study for data collection. Second, a personalised prevention program based on AI models and a self-assessment app will be developed during the project. This software will be tested and validated in interventional studies in the clinical sites. As the devices will be used for medical purposes, the **EU Medical Device Regulation (MDR)** applies. The MDR lays down requirements for clinical investigations of medical devices.

2.3.1 Medical devices for data collection

During the prospective research study, data will be collected using several medical devices, some provided by third-parties and others developed by partners of the consortium: **iBreve**, **HRI**, **ULMA**, **Particle**, and **SNSI**. Some of these devices (iBreve and SNSI) are still at the investigational stage or will be developed specifically for the project (CAMEL App ecosystem by Particle) and will be used **for data collection only**.

Whenever the purpose of a study with medical devices is to demonstrate that a device is ready to be put on the market and to be used in a clinical context, such a study is considered a **conformity assessment**.⁴³ Conformity assessments of medical devices are subject to the requirements of Article 62 MDR.

Currently however, no such conformity assessment is foreseen for the medical devices of these partners. Since the medical devices in the project are at an early stage of development, not in preparation for market introduction, nor even at a pilot stage, Article 62 of the MDR does not apply. The medical devices are, however, subject to the **requirements of the MDR aimed at “other clinical investigations”**,⁴⁴ as listed in Article 82 MDR. The most relevant requirements for the consortium partners are the following:

- The clinical investigation shall be designed and conducted in such a way that the rights, safety, dignity and well-being of the participants are protected and prevail over all other interests. The **clinical data** generated must be scientifically valid, reliable and robust and subject to scientific review.⁴⁵
- The investigation shall be subject to ethical review by an **ethics committee** in accordance with national law and may only proceed after a positive opinion.⁴⁶
- Participants must have given **informed consent**.⁴⁷

⁴³ Article 2(40) MDR.

⁴⁴ See Recital 71 MDR: “This Regulation should cover clinical investigations intended to gather clinical evidence for the purpose of demonstrating conformity of devices and should also lay down basic requirements regarding ethical and scientific assessments for other types of clinical investigations of medical devices”.

⁴⁵ Article 62(3) MDR.

⁴⁶ Article 62(3) and 62(4)(b) MDR.

⁴⁷ Article 62(4)(f) MDR.

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- **Participants' rights** to physical and mental integrity, privacy and the protection of their personal data (in accordance with the GDPR) must be safeguarded.⁴⁸
- The devices must conform to applicable **general safety and performance requirements**, and every precaution must be taken to protect the health and safety of the subjects, including appropriate technical and biological safety testing, pre-clinical evaluation, and provisions in the field of occupational safety and accident prevention, taking into account the state of the art.⁴⁹
- The **investigator** must have the professional qualifications required by national law, and other personnel involved must be suitably qualified to perform their tasks.⁵⁰

Moreover, Member States can define **additional requirements** in order to protect the rights, safety, dignity and well-being of participants and the scientific and ethical integrity of clinical investigations.⁵¹ This might include notification requirements to certain committees or bodies. **Partners should be aware of such requirements in their countries and comply with them.**

2.3.2 Development of software as a medical device

The MDR also covers **software** that is intended by the manufacturer to be used for a specific human medical purpose, including for **diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction or prognosis of disease**. Therefore, this definition might apply to the App ecosystem and the AI enabled digital tools for cardiovascular disease risk stratification developed in the project.

An essential aspect in determining the applicability of the MDR is the '**intended purpose**' of the device – in this case, the software. This refers to the manufacturer's stated use of the device, which is typically indicated on the label, in the instructions for use, or in promotional or sales materials.

The *Medical Device Coordination Group* (MDCG) has published guidelines to help manufacturers determine whether their software qualifies as a medical device.⁵² Some key points from the MDCG Guidelines are as follows:

- The MDCG defines software as “a set of instructions that processes input data and creates output data”.
- The MDR does not apply to software that *does not perform an action on data* or that *purely performs storage, archival, communication, simple search, or lossless compression*.
- Moreover, only software that **performs an action for the benefit of individual patients** is medical device software and thus covered by the MDR.

⁴⁸ Article 62(4)(h) MDR.

⁴⁹ Article 62(4)(l) MDR.

⁵⁰ Article 62(6) MDR.

⁵¹ Article 82(2) MDR.

⁵² MDCG 2019-11 Guidance on Qualification and Classification of Software in Regulation (EU) 2017/745 – MDR and Regulation (EU) 2017/746 – IVDR (October 2019). Accessible at: https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-09/md_mdcg_2019_11_guidance_qualification_classification_software_en_0.pdf

Examples of software that is or is not considered a medical device, according to the MDCG, are provided in the table below.

Software that does NOT perform an action for the benefit of individual patients	Software that performs an action for the benefit of individual patients
Software intended solely to provide generic diagnostic or treatment pathways, not directed to individual patients.	Decision support software which combines general medical information databases and algorithms with patient-specific data.
Software intended solely to aggregate population data.	Software intended to provide healthcare professionals or users with recommendations for diagnosis, prognosis, monitoring and treatment of individual patients.
Software intended solely for epidemiological studies or registers, or scientific literature, medical atlases, models and templates.	
Not medical device software; MDR does not apply	Medical device software; MDR applies

Table 4 Examples of software that is or is not considered a medical device

So, the intended purpose of the software as described by the manufacturer is paramount for its qualification as medical device software and for its further risk classification.

The project intends to develop an ecosystem of mobile applications (Apps) dedicated to support the self-assessment, data capture and monitoring and self-management of the participants in the CAMEL prospective studies. In addition, the project also ambitions to develop a *stratification scheme for cardiovascular disease personalised prevention*. The CAMEL grant agreement mentions that this stratification scheme will be based on AI models. It is presented as a personalized, cardiovascular disease risk assessment, clinical decision support system. The planned system will use **individual patient measurements** to offer personalized risk assessment.

Given the above, the **intended use** of this system and its components (computational models) must be carefully considered. Depending on the purpose for which the system is intended, it will be qualified as a medical device software covered by the MDR, or as software not covered by MDR. For instance, models providing recommendations for treatment of individual patients would be qualified differently (i.e., as medical device software covered by the MDR) compared to models that provide generic diagnostic or treatment pathways related to patient populations (i.e., software not covered by MDR).

2.4 European Health Dataspace Regulation

Health data in the EU is also regulated by the **European Health Data Space Regulation (EHDSR)**, which has been approved by the Council of the EU and is set to enter into force in the coming weeks.⁵³ The EHDSR aims to strengthen patients' rights over their health data

⁵³ Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Health Data Space and amending Directive 2011/24/EU and Regulation (EU) 2024/2847. Council approved version available on: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/PE-76-2024-INIT/en/pdf>. The publication in the EU Official Journal is expected at the beginning of March, and so the Regulation will enter into force 20 days later.

while ensuring seamless and secure access to electronic health records across Member States⁵⁴.

2.4.1 Primary and secondary use of electronic health data

The EHDSR establishes a governance framework for both primary and secondary use of **electronic health data** – hereafter referred to as “e-health data”.

E-health data includes both personal (health data in electronic form that falls within the scope of the GDPR) and non-personal data (e-health data outside the GDPR’s scope).⁵⁵ As defined under the EHDSR, e-health data encompasses all types of health data, regardless of whether it originated from the patient or another party, such as a healthcare professional. It also includes inferred and derived data, such as test results, diagnostics, medical examinations, as well as data that is automatically observed and recorded.⁵⁶

The EHDSR provides a **governance framework** for two types of uses of e-health data:

- **Primary use** refers to using a person’s e-health data to provide health services that assess, maintain or restore their state of health. This includes prescription, dispensation and provision of medicinal products and medical devices, as well as relevant social security, administrative, or reimbursement services.⁵⁷
- **Secondary use** refers to using e-health data for purposes that benefit society, such as research, innovation, policy-making, patient safety, personalised medicine, official statistics or regulatory activities. E-health data for these purposes can be initially collected in the context of primary use (for healthcare), but it can also be collected directly for secondary use purposes.⁵⁸

It is this ‘**secondary use**’ of e-health data that is important for the project. This chapter provides more information on the EHDSR’s requirements for the secondary use of e-health data in the following sections.

2.4.2 Sharing e-health data for research purposes

The secondary use of e-health data, which involves reusing data for research and other authorized purposes, engages three primary actors: health data access bodies, data holders, and data users. The table below provides a brief overview of key obligations applicable to each actor. For a comprehensive list, see Chapter IV of the EHDSR

Actor	Definition	Responsibilities
Health data access	Authorities set up by Member States	The HDAB will act as intermediaries between the data holders and potential users of the data (e.g. researchers,

⁵⁴ Article 1 EHDSR.

⁵⁵ Article 2(2)(c) EHDSR.

⁵⁶ Recital 6 EHDSR.

⁵⁷ Article 2(2)(d) EHDSR.

⁵⁸ Article 2(2)(e) EHDSR.

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body (HDAB)		<p>companies wishing to use the data for their research and development, patients).</p> <p>They will be in charge of granting access to e-health data for secondary purposes, examining applications for potential users to access data, issue data permits, pre-process requested data by compiling it from various data holders, maintaining national dataset catalogues with a list of available datasets, informing the public about conditions under which health data is made available, and enforcing obligations of the EHDSR vis-à-vis data users and data holders.⁵⁹</p>
Data holder	<p>(1) A natural or legal person, (2) who is in the healthcare sector, develops health products or performs health or care research, (3) and who has a legal right or obligation to process e-health data, or who has technical control over a product with e-health data.⁶⁰</p>	<p>Data holders who have received public funding must make available the data they have collected and processed to HDAB. The aim is to maximize the impact of public investment while also supporting research, innovation, patient safety, and policy making for the benefit of society.⁶¹</p> <p>Data holders also obligated to make certain categories of e-health data available for secondary use, including the content of electronic health records, social, environmental, and behavioural determinants of health, e-health data from biobanks and dedicated databases, and health-related administrative data.⁶²</p> <p>Data holders may provide a Union data quality and utility label on their datasets if they fulfil principles defined by the EHDSR and delegated acts. For some data sets, such as the ones created under EU Horizon projects, adherence to those principles is mandatory. In such case, the data holder should have 'sufficient documentation' for the HDAB to confirm the accuracy of the label.⁶³</p>
Data user	<p>Natural or legal person who has lawful access to e-health data for secondary use.⁶⁴</p>	<p>Applicants who want to access e-health data must apply for a data permit through the HDAB. For this they need to provide relevant information so that the HDAB can evaluate their data permit request.⁶⁵</p> <p>Once approved, data users can access and process e-health data in accordance with the data permit. However,</p>

⁵⁹ Articles 55-59 EHDSR.

⁶⁰ Article 2(2)(t) EHDSR.

⁶¹ Recital 59 EHDSR.

⁶² Article 51 EHDSR.

⁶³ Articles 60 and 78 EHDSR.

⁶⁴ Article 2(2)(u) EHDSR.

⁶⁵ Article 69 EHDSR.

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		<p>they will need to make the results or output of their secondary use of e-health data public, within 18 months from the completion of the processing, and such output should only contain anonymised data, and they must acknowledge the sources of the e-health data (the fact that it has been obtained under the EHDSR).⁶⁶ Data users must also make available the enriched dataset to the original data holder free of charge.</p> <p>Additionally, data users must inform the HDAB of any clinically significant findings that may affect the health of individuals in the dataset.</p>
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Table 5 Overview of obligations of actors for secondary use of e-health data

2.4.3 Secure processing environments

The EHDSR also regulates how HDAB shall provide data users with access to e-health data. A central concept for this is the ‘**secure processing environment**’ or ‘**SPE**’.

Data holders, on the one hand, should upload e-health data in the SPE. They must furnish the data in **anonymised** form. If anonymised data is insufficient for the intended purpose, it may be **pseudonymised**; in that case, only the HDAB should have access to the information needed to reverse the pseudonymisation.

Data users, on the other hand, can only access e-health data in the SPE. Moreover, they are only allowed to download non-personal e-health data from the SPE. Access to data through a SPE requires compliance with technical and organizational measures, security, and interoperability requirements.

SPE should meet certain **security criteria**:⁶⁷

- **Access restriction.** Access to the SPE must be limited to authorized persons listed in the respective data permit.
- **Risk minimization.** The risk of unauthorized reading, copying, modification, or removal of e-health data in the SPE should be minimized through state-of-the art technological means.
- **Limited access.** Only a limited number of authorized identifiable individuals should have access to the input, inspection, modification, or deletion of e-health data in the SPE.
- **Confidentiality.** Data users must have access only to the e-health data covered by their data permit, through individual and unique user identities and confidential access modes.
- **Log keeping.** Identifiable logs of access to the SPE must be maintained for a period necessary to verify and audit all processing operations in that environment.

⁶⁶ Article 61 EHDSR.

⁶⁷ Article 73 EHDSR

- **Compliance monitoring.** Security measures must be monitored and enforced to ensure compliance and mitigate potential security threats.

2.4.4 Fees for providing access to data

The HDAB may charge fees for making e-health data available for secondary use, and data holders can ask the HDAB for compensation of their costs in preparing the requested e-health data.⁶⁸ The fees may cover the costs related to evaluating data applications, granting data permits or providing answers to data requests. The fees charged must be reasonable and must take into account the interests of SMEs, individual researchers, and public bodies. Disputes regarding fee amounts will be resolved through dispute settlement bodies established under the Regulation EU 2023/2854 (i.e. the Data Act⁶⁹).

2.4.5 Caramel's compliance with EHDS

For more details on how CAMEL will comply with the EHDSR please see Section 2.5 of D1.3 "Data Management Plan".

2.5 Non-European Countries

2.5.1 Colombia

The CAMEL project in Colombia must comply with the following laws and regulations:

DATA PROTECTION LAW

Colombia's **Habeas Data Law** (hereinafter referred to as **Law 1581**) establishes the legal framework for personal data protection, ensuring that individuals have control over their personal information. Law 1581 outlines several key principles that form the foundation of personal data protection in Colombia, these being:

- **Consent Requirement:** Organizations must obtain prior, explicit, and informed consent before processing personal data, except in certain cases where consent is not required (e.g., legal obligations, public interest, medical emergencies, or historical/statistical purposes);
- **Security and Confidentiality:** Personal data must be protected against unauthorized access, loss, or disclosure;
- **Data Subject Rights:** Individuals have the right to access, update, correct, or delete their data, and may enforce these rights before both judges and the **Superintendence of Industry and Commerce (SIC)**, which is the Colombian data supervisory authority.

⁶⁸ Article 62 EHDSR.

⁶⁹ Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data.

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The law ensures high standards of personal data protection, with stricter safeguards for sensitive data and children's data.

International data transfers

Colombian law prohibits international transfers of personal data unless the recipient country provides data privacy and protection standards at least equivalent to those established by Colombian law. If the recipient country does not ensure the same level of protection, the data controller must either obtain explicit authorization from the data subject, or implement alternative legal mechanisms, such as contractual safeguards or SIC-approved security measures.

The SIC maintains a list of countries deemed to provide an adequate level of protection. This list primarily includes all **EU Member States** and other countries that the European Commission has recognized as ensuring an essentially equivalent level of data protection through an adequacy decision (e.g., **Israel**).

Compliance in the CAMEL Project

KER, the Colombian partner in the consortium, will comply with these regulations when transferring pseudonymised data to the CAMEL data lake within the framework of CAMEL-OS and CAMEL-IS. Since the EU Member States involved in the project and Israel are deemed by the SIC to provide an adequate level of protection, no special safeguards are required for these transfers. All data transfers will be conducted in accordance with SIC guidelines, ensuring full compliance with Colombian data protection laws.

ETHICAL GUIDELINES FOR HEALTH-RELATED RESEARCH

Colombia's **ethical guidelines for health-related research** are primarily governed by **Resolution 8430 of 1993** and align with international frameworks such as the Declaration of Helsinki, CIOMS (Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences) Guidelines, and Good Clinical Practice (GCP) standards.

Resolution 8430 establishes the scientific, technical, and administrative standards for research involving human participants and classifies research into three risk categories:

- **No Risk (Sin riesgo)** – Studies that do not interfere with participants, such as **retrospective research using existing data**, medical records, or publicly available anonymised information.
- **Minimal Risk – (Riesgo mínimo)** – Studies that involve **non-invasive procedures**, such as surveys, interviews, or the collection of biological samples through non-risky methods (e.g., saliva collection).
- **More than Minimal Risk (Riesgo mayor que el mínimo)** – Studies that involve interventions or procedures with potential risks to participants, including drug trials, surgical procedures, or studies exposing participants to physical, psychological, or social risks.

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Studies involving minimal or higher risk require approval from an accredited **Research Ethics Committee (Comité de Ética en Investigación)** or **Institutional Review Board (IRB)** before proceeding. Additionally, research involving vulnerable populations, such as children, pregnant women, or indigenous communities, requires additional ethical safeguards.

Moreover, researchers conducting human-related studies must adhere to such ethical principles such as:

- **Respect for autonomy** – which requires obtaining **informed consent** from participants.
- **Beneficence and non-maleficence** – which means ensuring the well-being and safety of participants.
- **Justice** – which translates into the equitable selection of participants and fair distribution of research benefits.

Researchers must comply with ethical standards and obtain Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval where required. Failure to comply with Resolution 8430 may result in administrative or legal sanctions, including suspension of research activities, financial penalties, or liability for harm caused to participants.

KER has a research policy that requires the approval of the Sanitas University Foundation's institutional Ethics Committee for the use of the organization's data or information into research.

2.5.2 Israel

The CAMEL project in Israel must adhere to Israel's data protection and human research regulations. Below is an overview of the relevant legal frameworks:

DATA PROTECTION LAW

Israel's data protection landscape is primarily governed by the **Protection of Privacy Law, 5741-1981 (PPL)**. This foundational legislation outlines the principles for collecting, processing, and securing personal data. In response to evolving global privacy standards, notably the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Israel enacted in 2018 **Amendment No. 13** to the PPL, which introduced significant updates to Israel's PPL enhancing data security and regulatory oversight.

The key principles for processing personal data mirror image those under the GDPR:

- **Transparency:** Inform individuals about how their data is collected and used.
- **Lawful Basis:** Ensure data collection is based on consent, legal authorization, public duty, or vital interests.
- **Purpose Limitation:** Use data only for specified purposes, as registered with the Israeli Registrar of Databases.
- **Data Minimisation:** Collect only necessary data and review it annually to ensure it's not excessive.
- **Proportionality:** Ensure data collection is proportionate to its purpose.
- **Retention:** Review and delete unnecessary data yearly once the purpose is complete.
- **Accuracy:** Keep data accurate and updated as per the data subject's rights.

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- **Accountability:** Demonstrate compliance with data processing principles through documentation, audits, and assigned privacy roles.

The Israeli privacy guidelines also suggest implementing GDPR-originated practices like Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) and appointing a privacy protection officer.

International data transfers

Amendment No. 13 to the PPL introduced specific guidelines regarding the transfer of personal data outside of Israel. Organizations transferring data abroad must ensure that the recipient country provides an adequate level of data protection. This ensures that personal data is not exposed to lower protection standards in foreign jurisdictions, thereby safeguarding Israeli citizens' information, even when it is processed internationally.

Transferring personal data from Israel to another country is generally prohibited unless the destination country provides a level of protection equal to or exceeding that of Israeli law.

Data transfers to EU Member States are allowed due to the European Commission's adequacy decision, which recognizes Israel's data protection standards as comparable to those of the EU. Also, Colombia's Law 1581 has been recognized by Israel's regulatory authorities as offering a level of protection that is sufficient for data transfers from Israel.

Compliance in the CAMEL Project

For the purpose of the CAMEL project, any data transfers between Israel and Colombia, or between Israel and EU Member States, can take place freely, as Israel considers both to ensure an adequate level of protection for personal data, similar to its own standards.

Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research

Israel's ethical guidelines for health-related research involving human participants are rooted in national laws designed to protect individuals' rights, dignity, and safety. The legal framework emphasizes the importance of respecting human dignity and privacy, ensuring that all research is conducted ethically and responsibly. Key legal principles are outlined in:

Basic Law: Human Dignity and Liberty (1992)

Approved by Knesset on March 17, 1992, this law guarantees the protection of an individual's life, body, and dignity, forming the foundation of ethical research in Israel. It ensures that human rights are central to any medical research, establishing that participants cannot be subjected to treatments or interventions that would violate their dignity or well-being.

Patient's Rights Act (1996):

This law provides additional protections for patients involved in medical research, with a particular focus on ensuring the dignity and privacy of participants.

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- **Safeguarding Patient Dignity:** All patients must be treated with respect at all stages of care, including during medical research. This includes avoiding any actions that could diminish the inherent worth of participants.
- **Safeguarding Patient Privacy:** The law emphasizes the importance of protecting patient confidentiality. Patient data can only be shared with third parties if explicit consent is given, or if legally required or necessary for continued care. This ensures that any personal health information remains secure.

A key aspect of Israel's ethical guidelines is the requirement for **informed consent**, ensuring that participants are fully aware of the nature of the research, its potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. This process is particularly important in protecting vulnerable populations, such as minors, individuals with cognitive impairments, or those who may be in a position of dependency. In these cases, additional safeguards are in place to ensure that consent is obtained ethically and that these populations are not exploited or coerced into participation. Researchers must ensure that the consent process is clear, voluntary, and free from undue influence, with special consideration given to the unique needs of these groups.

Research approval process

Before conducting research that involves human participants or patient data, approval must be obtained from relevant institutional and ethical committees to ensure compliance with the law and ethical guidelines:

- **Institutional Review Board (IRB):** All research involving human participants, including retrospective studies using clinical data, requires approval from a medical centre's IRB. This board evaluates the ethical implications of the proposed research and ensures that participants' rights and safety are prioritized.
- **Institutional Data Utilization Committee:** For research within Clalit Health Services, approval from this committee is also necessary to ensure that patient data is handled according to ethical and legal standards.
- **Ethics Committee Approval:** As mandated by the Patient's Rights Law, all health-related research must receive approval from an ethics committee to guarantee that the study adheres to ethical principles and that the rights of participants are safeguarded.

Israel's regulations ensure that health-related research is conducted in a manner that respects human dignity, prioritizes patient privacy, and adheres to ethical principles. Failure to adhere to these guidelines can result in legal consequences, including the suspension of research or penalties for non-compliance, safeguarding participants and ensuring the integrity of the research process.

3. Ethical Principles

CAMEL Ethics and Gender Guidelines and procedures comply with ethical principles and the highest standards of research integrity, including the ethical regulations and recommendations presented in the previous section. In order to ease the compliance of the planned research to these principles, and EU and national regulations. DCU with the support of TCD and TLX will deliver an “**Ethics and Gender Guidelines**” (Deliverable D1.3), in what can be considered as a companion of this Data Management Plan, with the overall ethics, legal, privacy and gender in research framework, applicable regulation and guidelines for the consortium.

3.1 Ethical Research Frameworks

Ethical conduct is a cornerstone and main characteristic in modern scientific research. Because scientific research often consults with human subjects directly and/ or indirectly, it is essential that special attention is paid to ethical scientific research. Within the Horizon research framework, we need to define three major directions of ethics in scientific and industrial research:

- **Academic discipline:** Ethics is the critical study of the norms that guide our actions.
- **Practical skills:** Ethics is the practical art of knowing how to apply moral principles in concrete situations.
- **Value systems:** Ethics deals with the core values that guide a person or an organisation on the way to its shared vision.

The European Commission defines the principles of European research ethics through the following points:

- **Respect for human dignity:** Respect for persons requires that subjects, to the degree that they are capable, are given the opportunity to choose what shall or shall not happen to them. This opportunity is provided when adequate standards for informed consent are satisfied, and these standards include:
 - **Information:** The extent and nature of information should be such that persons, knowing that the procedure is neither necessary for their care nor perhaps fully understood, can decide whether they wish to participate in the furthering of knowledge. In other words, the information should be sufficient so that a "reasonable volunteer" can decide whether to participate.
 - **Comprehension:** Information should be provided to potential subjects in such a way that they could understand what is being conveyed. Because the participant's ability to understand is a function of intelligence, rationality, maturity and language, it is necessary to adapt the presentation of the information to the participant's capacities. In CAMEL, investigators will be responsible for writing the Participant Information Sheets in a way that participants can comprehend the information.
 - **Voluntariness:** An agreement to participate in research constitutes a valid consent only if voluntarily given. While research participation is rarely coerced, undue influence can be part of the consent process when there is inequitable social pressure or there are inappropriate rewards to participate.

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- **Privacy:** This involves respecting an individual's right to privacy, the right to control access to one's self and information, and protecting the confidentiality of private, identifiable information about individuals. The CAMEL consortium will ensure that the participant's right of privacy is not violated and the confidentiality of information is protected. It will be clearly specified which data are collected, how they are processed, and who can access them. Privacy problems exist wherever uniquely identifiable data relating to a person or persons are collected and stored, in digital form or otherwise. Improper or non-existent disclosure control can be the root cause for privacy issues. The challenge in data privacy is to share data while protecting personal identity. The most common sources of data that are affected by data privacy issues are:
 - Health information
 - Criminal justice information
 - Financial information
 - Genetic information
 - Location information
 - Cultural information
 - Religious and political convictions
 - Ethnicity information
- **Beneficence:** The principle of beneficence includes the obligation of researchers to strive to do no harm and to maximize benefits and minimize harms. For the fulfilment of the ethical standards of this principle, a series of procedures should be kept in mind:
 - Systematic assessment of risk and benefits: There is need to determine that the risks are justified by the research's anticipated benefits. Risk does not mean harm, but it is the possibility of harm, and an analysis of the risks must consider both the magnitude of the possible harm and the probability that the harm may occur. The research's anticipated benefits may be to the individual research participants, or they may be to others in the form of the advancement of scientific knowledge.
 - Minimization of risks: In addition to determining that the risks are reasonable in relation to the anticipated benefits, the principle of beneficence requires that the risks in the research are the minimum required to achieve the research objective. Where necessary, alternative, less risky procedures or modifications to the procedures need to be explored that reduce the magnitude or probability of the possible harm to subjects. This links with the principle of Non-Maleficence (which involves causing no harm, or the least harm that is possible in comparison to the benefits obtained).
- **Justice:** The principle of justice requires that the selection of participants is equitable. The principle of justice requires a fair sharing of the burdens and benefits of research and that groups are not exploited because of their circumstances. The selection of participants must be based on the research's scientific needs, not on convenience in recruitment. Researchers should be able to scientifically justify the inclusion or exclusion of participants.
- **Proportionality:** The level of information collection must be limited to what it is strictly necessary. If the same information can be collected by less invasive procedures, and in less time, the researchers must follow procedures that ensure that the information is

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collected in a way that collects the minimum amount of data and minimizes the inconveniences to the participant.

- **Utility:** Information must not be collected unless the goal to do it is clearly specified. It directly links to proportionality, respect and privacy. The technologies involved in the CAMEL project will collect the minimum amount of information that is necessary for the goals of the project, and this will be clearly specified in the study protocol for each research stage.
- **Autonomy:** This implies that each participant may decide what is better for them and that must be respected. The individual may experience autonomy each time they perceive that their behaviour is congruent and self-initiated. Participants in CAMEL need to be in control of the decision-making in terms of their desire to participate, stay and leave the project at any time they consider.
- **Integrity:** This implies that physical, psychological and social conditions of the participants must be respected and that nobody can violate them without an explicit and informed consent. In CAMEL, no physical harm is predicted. Slight physical discomfort may be experienced for participants providing biomedical data (e.g. blood samples) but this will be minimised by collecting data as part of normal care when and wherever possible. Psychological factors such as anxiety may be involved if the participants have a concern about their privacy and social factors such as embarrassment may be felt (especially in focus group and/or workshop settings) as participants describe their experiences and needs. These issues will be properly addressed and documented in the informed consent forms for each of the different CAMEL clinical studies.
- **Transparency:** The goals and purpose of data collection must be clearly explained to the participants, and, where necessary, to relatives. It links directly with the nature and features of the informed consent form.

3.2 Testing with Human Participants

The involvement of human participants in the co-design and validation of CAMEL requires strict adherence to rules of law and professional conduct regarding ethics. Research will be conducted in the spirit of the Helsinki declaration and the Oviedo Bioethics Convention, and will commit to abide strictly to the principles of:

- Respecting human dignity
- Ensuring honesty and transparency towards participants and notably getting free and informed consent, as well as assent and/or rolling consent whenever relevant
- Protecting vulnerable persons
- Protecting individuals against exploitation arising out of treatment or research
- Ensuring privacy and confidentiality
- Sharing the benefits with disadvantaged populations
- Following the highest standards of research integrity (i.e. avoiding any kind of fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, unjustified double funding, or other type of

research misconduct) as defined in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity⁷⁰.

3.2.1 Participant recruitment

We will recruit three groups of participants across four clinical studies.

Clinical Studies	Study Description	Participant Groups
CAMEL-WOMEN	Mixed Method study for co-design of CAMEL apps (WP4). This will enable us to better understand women-specific risk factors, women's experiences and barriers in CVD prevention to determine the overall requirements for the project and subsequent clinical studies	Participants will be women (N=7000), clinicians engaged in CVD risk-reduction and women's health (N=30) from 6 countries. In addition, 50-100 women with intellectual disabilities (ID) will also be recruited to participate in a face-to-face survey. Participants will indicate if they are willing to be recontacted for further participation. Of those that agree, 15-20 will be contacted to take part in individual interviews or focus groups.
CAMEL-RS	Study 2: CAMEL RS. Retrospective Study for EHR-based incident prediction modelling and temporal disease trajectory analysis	Retrospective data will be included from females with a minimum age of 40 at beginning of observation and maximum age of 60 at index date. Processing is compatible with the purposes for which initial consent was sought so no additional consent is required. ⁷¹
CAMEL-OS	Study 3: CAMEL OS. Prospective Observational Study for women CVD-RA modelling and stratification with multiple data sources.	Participants will be women (N=3000), 40 - 60 years of age and representative of 4 CVD risk profiles following CAMEL initial stratification across 6 clinical sites (ca 500 per site). <u>CVD risk profiles:</u> L1 – women with low risk profiles L2 – more often younger, women with abnormal biomarkers and/or diagnosed HT/DY in primacy care L3 – women who already present high atherosclerotic risk and are under treatment L4 – women who already had CVD events
CAMEL-IS	Study 4: CAMEL IS. Prospective Interventional study for women CVD monitoring and self-management	Participants will be women (N=1,200) 40-40 years of age without life threatening disease non-related to CVD across 5 clinical sites. N=600 (Intervention) and N=600 (Control) distributed across the 4 CVD risk profiles.

Table 6 Participant recruitment for CAMEL Clinical Studies

70 ALLEA (2023) The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023. Berlin. DOI 10.26356/ECOC

71 Article 5.1(a) and 5.1(b) of GDPR; <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-5-gdpr/>

3.2.2 Informed consent procedures

The study will be explained to the potential participant verbally, providing all pertinent information (purpose, procedures, risks, benefits, alternatives to participation), and allow the potential participant ample opportunity to ask questions or voice concerns. The consent document will not be read verbatim but, rather, the information will be rephrased, comprehension will be checked and allowing for questions will be allowed throughout the process. The documents and explanations provided by the facilitator will also be tailored to the inclusion in CAMEL-WOMEN of a sample of women with intellectual disabilities. To ensure accessibility and inclusivity, easy-to-read information will be provided, and a Total Communication Approach (TCA) implemented with participants with intellectual disabilities. This approach includes a visual representation of all materials, LÁMH sign language, modelling, and augmented communication as necessary for each potential participant. Informed consent will be recorded using a signed easy-to-read consent form. Consent will be sought at least 7 days after the participant has received the information pack, which includes a cover letter, a Participant Information Leaflet (PIL), and the consent form (ICF) in easy-to-read format.

Selected participants will be invited to meet the researchers to explain the project further and seek explicit consent. Participants with intellectual disability will be supported to express their choice and to make an independent decision participating in this project.

Explicit consent will be obtained from all participants in accordance with the assumption of capacity outlined in The Assisted Decision-Making (Capacity) 2015 (Amendment) Act 2022. This capacity pertains specifically to the decision to participate in the study and is not generalized; consent capacity is assumed until proven otherwise. If a participant with an intellectual disability is unable to provide explicit consent independently, they will not be included in the study. The Participant Information Leaflet clearly explains that participants can contact researchers for further information and discuss the information pack with their support person before making a decision if needed. Additionally, potential participants are encouraged to involve their keyworker or a family member, who may accompany them to their interview, if they wish. Patient and Public Involvement (PPI) engagement by adults with intellectual disabilities has been integrated into the proposed activities. Specifically, PPI engagement has included consultation with a TCAID employee and Ambassador liaison officer with an intellectual disability in the development of accessible materials.

Recognising the participation of women with intellectual disabilities, who may be at risk of safeguarding, adequate anonymisation and data protection measures will be crucial in this study. Participant documentation (e.g. recruitment notices, study information sheets, consent forms) will provide comprehensible information, developed in easy-to-read formats, and accessible to individuals with mild to moderate levels of intellectual disability. All materials will meet European Easy Read Standards^{72,73}. Thus, ensuring that all participants, including women with intellectual disabilities, fully understand their rights when deciding if they will become involved in the study and that fully informed consent will be obtained from all.

All participants will be enabled to provide self-consent, ensuring their autonomy and rights are upheld throughout the research process. Furthermore, a data protection impact assessment

72 <https://www.inclusion-europe.eu/easy-to-read-standards-guidelines/>

73 <https://op.europa.eu/documents/d/accessibility/easy-to-read-guidelines>

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(DPIA) will be conducted as part of the CAMEL Data Management Plan (DMP). This assessment will address any potential risks or ethical concerns associated with the participation of women, including women with intellectual disabilities, in the CAMEL studies, and ensure that their rights and dignity are respected at all stages of the research process.

Information packs will be sent in advance. At least 7 days but typically three to four weeks will have elapsed since participants received the information pack, ensuring ample time for consideration before providing their consent. Questions will be answered and asked to further the discussion and elicit any additional questions from the potential participant. This will prompt the potential participant to think carefully about the study. On agreement to take part in the study, the participant will sign and date the IRB approved consent form.

In accordance with ethical practice in studies with human participants, CAMEL partners will strictly follow international rules and ethical considerations of the participants. These include personal freedom, autonomy, privacy and responsibility, and participants have the right to decline or withdraw whenever they want, even if they have previously given consent, without giving any reason for having done so. All activities involving participants will take place only after ethical approval has been granted from the appropriate institutional/regional/national ethics bodies and informed consent has been obtained from the participants. Consent forms and participant information sheets will clearly state the purpose and benefits of the research, associated risks and discomforts (if any) resulting from participating in the study. The form will also provide explicit statement and explanation of the rights deriving from GDPR and a contact person for exercising those rights. Participants will be thoroughly debriefed following participation and provided with details for supports suitable for and relevant to each participant.

DCU, as Chair of the GLED Committee, and all GLED Committee members will review the protocols for each CAMEL study to ensure that all ethical dimensions, including the provision of informed consent, have been considered in all the research activities.

3.2.3 Incidental findings

Given the nature of the study, CVD risk, CVD and/or other difficulties may be detected in otherwise healthy adults (L1). The full extent of CVD risk, CVD and/or other difficulties detected in those participating in the study (L2 to L4) might also be greater than previously detected. Where CVD risk and/or disease are detected, these findings will be incorporated in the treatment and care plans as usual at each of the clinical sites. Where other difficulties are detected that might be a cause for concern, participants will be advised to consider consulting their General Practitioner (GP) for further evaluation.

Another potential issue could be related to the safe installation of devices, sensors and technologies in clinical settings and/or for use by participants. The consortium will ensure and certify that the use of technologies involved in the CAMEL project is safe for the individual, that no harm of any kind is expected due to the use of the technology involved in the project in order to guarantee that both the integrity of the equipment and the participants are considered, covered and guaranteed. Potential adverse events related to the use of technology will be constantly monitored and reported when necessary.

To ensure participant safety, he/she/they will be informed that if, at any time, the principal investigator determines it is not in the best interest of the participant to continue in the study (e.g. in case of increased risk), the person will be advised to withdraw from the study.

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In case of an incidental finding that requires further assessment, the partner that detects the finding has the responsibility to communicate this issue as a potential conflict for the ethical integrity of the project to the GLED Committee. When the issue is minor (e.g. differences on how to ask a particular question between partners from different countries with different cultures) and can be solved within the consortium, corrective measures will be adopted. When the potential ethical issue (e.g. a confidentiality breach) implies decision making and expertise beyond the scope of the CAMEL consortium, the project team will seek further assistance from external ethical review boards.

3.2.4 Ethical Approval

All partners who will be dealing with human participants will be subject to the governance and control of ethical committees in place at the institutional (central) level of their respective organisations. Ethical approval must be sought and obtained prior to commencing participant recruitment at the clinical site and at any other collaborating organisation involved in data collection. Fully informed consent must be sought from the participants prior to any data collection. The ethical approval procedures for each clinical partner are presented in Table 7.

Partner	Clinical Studies	Ethics Committee	Ethical Approval Procedures
ASC/Spain	CARMEL-RS	Comité de Ética de la Investigación con medicamentos (CEIm) de Hospital Clinic de Barcelona	<p>ASCIREs will submit the CARMEL-RS protocol to our reference <i>Comité de Ética de Investigación con Medicamentos</i> (CEIm) for ethical approval. The approval process involves submitting all required documents for the committee's review, including the protocol, the principal investigator's declaration, and a checklist covering legal and ethical compliance.</p> <p>Once the committee reviews the submission, it issues a report. If modifications or clarifications are required, a deadline is set for their submission. After all the comments have been addressed, the committee makes a final decision.</p> <p>The committee meets twice a month and typically responds within a week. On average, protocol approval takes approximately two months, though the timeline may vary depending on the number of required clarifications.</p>
BIO/Spain	CARMEL-WOMEN CARMEL-RS CARMEL-OS	Comité de Ética de la Investigación con Medicamentos (CEIm-s) de Euskadi	<p>The procedure for obtaining ethical approval in BIO involves submitting a standardized application form to the <i>Comité de Ética de la Investigación con Medicamentos de Euskadi</i> (CEIm-E). The submission is done online, and the deadline is 10 days before the next scheduled meeting (which is set in advance and published on the official Euskadi.eus website at the beginning of each year). Feedback is usually received within a week. If clarifications are needed, the chair may require the proposal to be revised and reconsidered at the subsequent meeting. This procedure is quite common and often delays the issuance of a favourable opinion.</p> <p>Modifications and/or responses can be submitted at any time as an amendment; however, it is recommended to submit the documents at least 2 days before the meeting. On the other hand, if only minor changes are made that do not affect the safety of participants or the validity of research results, they can be included in the application along with a cover letter notifying the committee.</p> <p>All data collection tools, advertising flyers, plain language statements, and consent forms must be included in the application.</p>
KER/Columbia	CARMEL-WOMEN	Comité de Ética de Investigación de la	The procedure for obtaining ethical approval in Colombia involves a standardized application form sent to the Comité de Ética en Investigación de

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	CAMEL-RS CAMEL-OS CAMEL-IS	Fundación Universitaria Sanitas	la Fundación Universitaria Sanitas. It is an online submission (Fundanet platform) and the submission date (which is fixed) is 1:00pm every first and third Friday. The project will be schedule to Research Commission before of the Ethical Committee review. The Commission is realized the second and fourth Thursday. In this meeting the researchers present the protocol and receive feedback one week after. In case the project receives feedback, the researcher must send a new version by online submission (Fundanet platform) within the month. With the protocol final version, the Comité de Ética en Investigación de la Fundación Universitaria Sanitas, review the protocol each Thursday and give a concept: Approval or require adjust within the month. All data collection tools, advertising flyers, plain language statements and consent forms must be included in the application. Note that no ethics reviews are conducted between mid-December and February.
MAG/Croatia	CAMEL- WOMEN CAMEL-RS CAMEL-OS CAMEL-IS	Ethics Committee of Magdalena Clinic	The meetings of the Committee are organized and convened by the Chairperson of the Committee, with an invitation including the proposed agenda and relevant documents sent at least 8 days before the meeting. After opening the meeting, the Chairperson must provide the necessary explanations regarding the meeting's proceedings. The Committee makes decisions or recommendations in the presence of the majority of its members. Decisions are made by consensus, and voting is conducted publicly by a show of hands or individually, with decisions adopted by a majority vote. The Governing Council and the Director of the clinic are informed of the decision. Minutes of the meeting are recorded.
NKUA/Greece	CAMEL- WOMEN CAMEL-RS CAMEL-OS CAMEL-IS	Ethics Committee of Aretaieion University Hospital of Greece, NKUA	The procedure for obtaining ethical approval in our clinical site in NKUA involves a standardized application form sent to the Ethics Committee of Aretaieion University Hospital. It is a written application form of the translated protocol, the consent form and the corresponding request form. The ethics committee meets every approximately three months. If there are clarifications, the chair may ask

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			for the submission of additional files and will examine them in a period shorter than one month. If there are small changes these can be made to the application with a cover letter for chair's decision. Note that no ethics reviews are conducted between end-July and August.
SAS/Spain	CAMEL-WOMEN CAMEL-RS CAMEL-OS CAMEL-IS	Comité Coordinador de Ética de la Investigación Biomédica de Andalucía (CCEIBA). Comité de Ética de Investigación de los Hospitales Universitarios Virgen Macarena-Virgen del Rocío.	<p>SAS' clinical research activities are conducted upon the clearance of the competent research ethics committee in the region. All applications are handled via a web application called SICEIA which allows researchers to submit all the requested documentation (study protocol, informed consent form, PI commitment to stick the protocol, economic plan, etc.) to their assigned committee. All ethics committees meet on a monthly basis.</p> <p>In CAMEL, for prospective studies (-WOMEN, -OS and -IS), clearance from the Virgen Macarena-Virgen del Rocío Univ. Hospitals Ethics Committee will be sought, while for retrospective study (-RS), the applications will first be submitted to the regional Coordinator of Biomedical Research Ethics Committee and, once cleared, a second application is needed to be submitted to the Regional Data Access Committee for Research Purposes, according to the regional law Joint Resolution 1/2021 (link to the official document in Spanish) which regulates the access and use of health data hosted by the SAS for research and innovation purposes. For this application, the following information must be attached to the application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data access request for research purposes form. • Research project, including the following items: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Methodology and work plan ○ Objectives, variables, and statistical analysis plan foreseen ○ Type of study: retrospective, prospective or transversal ○ Specific data types and variables requested, including estimated size ○ Applicability and impact for our regional public health system

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Planning, including foreseen start date for data processing and project end date ○ CVs of Principal researcher and research team ○ Participating centres ● Informed consent (whenever applies, according to current regulation) ● Details about the sponsor or funder. ● Clearance from the ethical committee. ● Data Protection Impact Assessment (as per the GDPR). ● Affidavit of confidentiality and non-reidentification. ● Affidavit of non-transference of data to third parties. ● Affidavit of non-transference of data outside the GDPR scope. ● Data processing/joint controllership agreement.
TCD/Ireland	CAMEL-WOMEN	Trinity College Dublin Ethics Committee	<p>In the Faculty of Health Sciences, Trinity College Dublin, ethics applications are routed through either the relevant School Research Ethics Committee (REC) where available, or through the Faculty of Health Sciences Ethics Committee. One exception to this is the Joint Research Ethics Committee (JREC) that serves two of our clinical partner sites and provides joint approval on behalf of the clinical site/s and the University. Ethics applications are made to the relevant school ethics committee where the project is of deemed low or very low risk, while those of moderate to high risk are made to the Faculty Research Ethics committee.</p> <p>An on-line ethics application system called the Research Ethics Application Management System (REAMS) was introduced in recent years and is currently being adopted throughout the university. Each REC meets monthly, with nine meetings annually. Submissions are due three to four weeks ahead of the scheduled meeting date. Feedback is received within a week and the outcomes include reject and resubmit, make revisions or approval granted. There are clear</p>

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			procedures and a reporting form for reporting an adverse event to the REC. An annual report form must be completed by applicants, in addition to an end of project report form.
VULSK/Lithuania	CAMEL-WOMEN CAMEL-RS CAMEL-OS CAMEL-IS	Vilnius Regional Biomedical Research Ethics Committee	In general, the Ethics Committee convenes on a monthly basis. To be included in a particular meeting (e.g. March 3 rd), all signed documents must be registered a month in advance (e.g. February 3 rd). Once a protocol is submitted, it typically takes the committee approximately one month to issue a decision. If any revisions or clarifications are requested, an additional month is usually required for reviewing those corrections.

Table 7 Ethical Approval Processes for Partners participating in CAMEL Clinical Studies

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The application for ethical approval will contain:

- A summary of the project.
- Research methodology and protocols, including how participants will be selected (inclusion and exclusion criteria), any risks associated with the project and how they will be managed.
- Participant Information Sheet (PIS) - information regarding the project, such as a lay (non-technical) description for potential participants adapted for each partner location.
- Informed consent forms adapted for participant group (e.g. women with ID) and for each partner location.
- Consent for data sharing adapted for types of data and for each partner location.
- All questionnaires, interview schedules, co-design workshop scripts and protocols.
- Description of any experimental technology and its components, providing a technology user manual with indication for use.

As detailed in Section 3.2.2, consent forms will clearly state the purpose and benefits of the research, any associated risks, discomforts and adverse side effects (if any) resulting from participating in the study. These forms will also provide an explanation of procedures to manage confidentiality concerning personal data, a contact person who can handle questions about the study and/or requests for withdrawal from the study, and any consequences that may result from withdrawing (e.g. any limitations to removal of participant data).

A full set of approved ethical documents (application and any appendices) and a copy of the ethical approval letter for each study will be sent to the GLED chair (DCU) by each partner on receipt. The GLED chair (DCU) will monitor the status of ethical application, ethical compliance and manage any ethical questions, issues or concerns as they arise (see Section 5). A review of the ethical conduct of the project will be included in all consortium plenary meetings and periodic reports.

3.3 Human Cells and Tissues

This proposal includes the use of human cells and tissues, specifically two categories of blood samples:

- Blood samples coming from the CoroPrevention cohort, whose informed consent will be managed by TAU as Project Coordinator. These samples will be stored in the high-quality liquid nitrogen farm at Tampere University (Finland).
- Blood samples coming from CAMEL-OS (Observational Study) and CAMEL-IS (Intervention Study) carried out in the six clinical sites. These will be securely shipped, stored and analysed in CIC's facilities in Spain.

Partners who use, produce or collect cells or tissues will obtain the necessary accreditation/designation/authorisation/licensing from the relevant Ethics Committees. Partners will also deliver periodic Biobank Activity Reports to the GLED with information on donors included/excluded, details of what was deposited, how the Biobank is managed, standard operating procedures that are in place, etc.

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Additionally, free and fully informed consent will be obtained from the donors of the cell blood samples to give permission for the use of the sample in the CAMEL project and in other research projects. In order to obtain this fully informed consent, clinical sites will ensure that the following information is contained in the participant information sheets and in consent forms:

- How CAMEL will keep track of the origin of cells and tissues that are used, produced or collected. This includes who is responsible for this task and where cells and tissues will be stored and accessed from.
- Indication of the national legislation under which these materials will be stored, how long it will be stored for, and what will happen at the end of the storage period.

3.4 Protection of Personal Data

Protecting personal data is crucial for upholding individual privacy and autonomy, ensuring individuals have control over their information and preventing potential harm from misuse or unauthorized access. Furthermore, safeguarding personal data fosters trust in organizations and promotes responsible data handling practices, which are essential for maintaining ethical standards and legal compliance. CAMEL's Data Management Plan (D1.2) details the key principles related to the protection of personal data. In summary, these include:

- **Compliance with Regulations:** The project is committed to adhering to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the AI Act (AIA), and the European Health Data Spaces (EHDS) Regulation.
- **Data Security:** CAMEL will implement data security procedures to ensure secure data management, in compliance ISO 27001 standards.
- **Data Protection:** All CAMEL data will be subject to appropriate safeguards for the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons in accordance with the GDPR and the requirements of the AI Act.
- **Pseudonymisation:** Using pseudonymisation techniques such as tracking participant (patient) data using a univocal code in all documents, only using this unique participant identification number to link data and samples, further encryption of patient identifiers at clinical sites where required (e.g. additional pseudonymisation for location data and date of birth). A confidential correspondence list, containing the code associated with each participant name and identity will be securely stored by the clinical sites separate to CAMEL data.
- **Data Processing Protection Principles:** Applying data processing protection principles enshrined in Art. 5 of the GDPR: lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimisation, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity and confidentiality.

3.5 Non-EU Countries

All partners, whether from EU or Non-EU countries will adhere to the ethical guidelines presented in this deliverable when preparing their ethics application. The following section present country-specific considerations for CAMEL partners in non-EU countries.

3.5.1 Colombia

All CAMEL clinical studies will be submitted to the Comité de Ética en Investigación de la Fundación Universitaria Sanitas for approval. Given that CAMEL involves clinical studies

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with imported devices, INVIMA - the Colombian regulatory agency, will also approve the wearables and/or other devices as relevant.

The Colombian partner (KER) additionally agrees to:

- Anonymise participant data using statistical techniques including permutation and randomisation of records in their analysis matrix. Personal data (all numerical, alphabetical, photographic, acoustic, or any other type of information to collection, registration, processing, and transmission concerning identified or identifiable natural persons such as name, surname, social security card number, identification personal information, telephone number, etc.) will not be included in the database for information analysis.
- Data will be hosted on a server that meets data security requirements as presented in the CAMEL DMP (D1.2), with exclusive and controlled access by research group members.

3.5.2 Israel

The Israeli partners (BGU, SNSI) will not collect data as part of the CAMEL studies, so neither will require an ethics application. Each partner will abide by the ethical and data guidelines for the use of participant data as detailed in this document and in the CAMEL Data Management Plan (D1.2).

3.6 Generative-AI

The integration of Generative-AI (GEN-AI) into research environments presents both opportunities and challenges necessitating the provision of guidelines that CAMEL researchers can rely on to ensure that its benefits are realised while risks are mitigated. The European Research Area (ERA) Forum has produced living guidelines⁷⁴ that address the responsible use of generative AI in research, targeting researchers, research organizations, and funding bodies. They aim to prevent misuse and promote the positive impact of AI on research practices. Key principles include:

- **Integrity and Reliability:** Gen-AI can produce convincing but potentially inaccurate or biased content. Ensuring the quality of research through careful design, methodology, analysis, and resource use, including verification and reproduction of AI-generated information helps maintain high standards.
- **Transparency and Accountability:** Recognising and disclosing the use of Gen-AI in research maintains transparency in research development, execution, review, reporting, and communication. It promotes accountability by ensuring that researchers take responsibility for research from its inception to publication, including its management, organization, training, supervision, mentoring, and wider societal impacts, underpinned by human agency and oversight.

⁷⁴ European Commission (2024) Living Guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2b6cf7e5-36ac-41cb-aab5-0d32050143dc_en?filename=ec_rtd_ai-guidelines.pdf

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- **Ethical Implications:** Gen-AI raises ethical concerns, such as privacy issues, intellectual property rights, and potential biases. Addressing these concerns is essential to ensure that research is conducted ethically.
- **Innovation and Progress:** Gen-AI can accelerate research by automating tasks, generating hypotheses, and analysing large datasets. However, its potential benefits must be balanced with careful consideration of its limitations and risks.
- **Collaboration, Trust and Respect:** Understanding and addressing the challenges posed by Gen-AI can foster collaboration and trust among researchers, policymakers, and the public. This collaboration is vital for advancing research while maintaining societal trust. Considering the limitations, environmental impact, and societal effects of AI, and properly managing information, respecting privacy, confidentiality, intellectual property rights, and providing proper citation are essential.
- **Regulatory Frameworks:** Developing guidelines and recommendations for the use of Gen-AI in research helps ensure compliance with legal and ethical standards, protecting both researchers and the public.
- **Education and Training:** Educating researchers about the appropriate use of Gen-AI tools is essential for maximising their benefits while minimising risks. This includes understanding AI's capabilities, limitations and potential biases.

These key principles have informed the following guidelines for CAMEL researchers:

1. **Responsibility for Scientific Output:** Researchers are accountable for the integrity of AI-generated content and must maintain a critical approach, recognizing the limitations of AI tools (bias, hallucinations, inaccuracies). AI systems cannot be authors, authorship lies with human researchers.
2. **Transparent Use of Generative AI:** Researchers should transparently detail which Gen-AI tools were substantially used in their research processes, including the tool's name, version, date, and how it affected the research.
3. **Privacy, Confidentiality and Intellectual Property Rights:** Researchers should not provide third parties' personal data to online Gen-AI systems unless the participant has provided informed consent for this specific purpose.
4. **Future-Proofing and Continuous Ethical Review:** Researchers should regularly monitor and reassess the ethical, regulatory, and technical landscape of Generative-AI to ensure ongoing compliance and responsible use. This includes staying informed about updates to the AI Act, GDPR, and emerging ethical guidelines while continuously refining bias mitigation, transparency, and sustainability strategies. To that end the GLED Committee will periodically check the update of the referred European Research Area (ERA) Forum's Living Guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research. Where applicable, researchers should engage in expert consultations or ethics reviews to assess new risks posed by AI advancements.

3.7 Trustworthy AI Models

This section describes the AI models in the project concisely, presents the assessment according to the seven Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) requirements, and explains how Trustworthy AI is implemented during the project.

The Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)⁷⁵ is a practical tool that helps business and organisations to self-assess the trustworthiness of their AI systems under development. The concept of Trustworthy AI was introduced by the High-Level Expert Group on AI (AI HLEG) in the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (AI) and is based on seven key requirements:

- **R1. Human Agency and Oversight**, including fundamental rights, human agency and human oversight.
- **R2. Technical Robustness and Safety**, including resilience to attack and security, fall back plan and general safety, accuracy, reliability and reproducibility.
- **R3. Privacy and Data Governance**, including respect for privacy, quality and integrity of data, and access to data
- **R4. Transparency**, including traceability, explain ability and communication.
- **R5. Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness**, including the avoidance of unfair bias, accessibility and universal design, and stakeholder participation.
- **R6. Environmental and Societal well-being**, including sustainability and environmental friendliness, social impact, society and democracy.
- **R7. Accountability**, including auditability, minimisation and reporting of negative impact, trade-offs and redress.

CAMEL will continuously monitor and adapt its AI governance strategy in alignment with evolving regulations, including updates to the AI Act and emerging ethical AI frameworks. This will ensure compliance with the latest standards while maintaining the highest levels of trustworthiness and fairness in AI-driven health research.

In the following sections, the ALTAI self-assessment is carried out for the overall AI modalities. Moreover, for each of the seven essential requirements the ethical requirements are also self-assessed as included in the “Ethics by Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence” guidance document⁷⁶ elaborated by Experts appointed by the DG Research & Innovation RTD.03.001-Research Ethics and Integrity Sector. Ethical requirements are highlighted in each case.

3.7.1 R.1. Human Agency and Oversight

Human Agency: The AI system is designed to implement data-driven, personalized approaches using large cohorts of individuals with the aim to identify CVD-risk factors. End-users, clinicians, and researchers will be made aware from the start about the knowledge and tools to comprehend and interact with the classification AI systems to a satisfactory degree and be enabled to self-assess or challenge the system reasonably. AI systems should support individuals in making better, more informed choices in accordance with their goals. The overall principle of user autonomy will be central to the system’s functionality. Key to this is the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing when it produces legal effects on users or significantly affects them.

⁷⁵ European Commission: Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, The Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self assessment, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/002360>

⁷⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-by-design-and-ethics-of-use-approaches-for-artificial-intelligence_he_en.pdf

Human Oversight: The project AI system(s), will follow the Human-in-Command (HIC) approach, referred to as the capability to oversee the overall activity of the AI system and the ability to decide when and how to use the AI system in any situation. This will include the decision not to use the AI system in a particular situation, to establish levels of human discretion during the use of the system, or to ensure the ability to override a decision made by an AI system.

R1 Ethical Requirements Check	
R1.1	End-users and others affected by the AI system are not deprived of the abilities to make all decisions about their own lives and/or have basic freedoms taken away from them.
R1.2	End-users and others affected by the AI system are not subordinated, coerced, deceived, manipulated, objectified or dehumanized, nor is attachment or addiction to the system and its operations being stimulated.
R1.3	The AI system does not autonomously make decisions about vital issues that are normally decided by humans by means of free personal choices or collective deliberations or similarly affects individuals.
R1.4	The AI system is designed in a way that gives system operators and, as much as possible, end-users the ability to control, direct and intervene in basic operations of the system (when relevant).

Table 8 Human Agency and Oversight Ethical Requirements

3.7.2 R2. Technical Robustness and Safety

The AI system(s) will be developed with a preventative approach to risks and will behave reliably and as intended while minimising unintentional and unexpected harm as well as preventing it where possible.

Security: The AI models will not be certified for cybersecurity, as they will not have to be compliant with such certification schemes. Nonetheless, the models will be built following security and privacy by design approaches considering the regulatory pathway that during and beyond the project might lead to the certification as a medical device of the future. The consortium will consider the principles promoted by the “MDCG (Medical Device Coordination Group) 2019-16 Guidance on Cybersecurity for medical devices” and will rely in the expertise of the Digital Security research unit, with a broad experience in the Cybersecurity field including the definition of AI based defensive measures against adversarial attacks, applied to different critical infrastructures including clinical and health related settings (KINAITICS project, HORIZON-CL3-2021-CS-01-03 funded project).

Safety: The risk of adversarial, critical or damaging impact in case of technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, inappropriate or malicious use to the system is assessed as low. Nonetheless, as referred, security by design measures will be put in place all along the AI Life Cycle of the AI models. In case of attack or malfunctioning, the clinician or researcher will be the one taking life affecting clinical decisions for their patients. A first step towards ensuring safety will be the determination of the optimal operation point. As the output of the models is sometimes a score and not a category, establishing a threshold for classification determines

the operation point in the ROC curve, which, for a binary test determines sensitivity and specificity.

Accuracy: Accuracy pertains to an AI system’s ability to make correct judgements, for example to correctly classify information into the proper categories, or its ability to make correct predictions, recommendations, or decisions based on data or models. The impact of a lack of accuracy is assessed as relevant in the proposed AI models. Considering this high-risk impact, an explicit and well-formed development and evaluation process has been put in place in order to support, mitigate and correct unintended risks from inaccurate predictions, indicating the accuracy rates of the classification and predictions how likely these errors are. To that end, it is necessary to ensure high quality and representativity of the training data. Whereas all models are imperfect, a proper selection, quality assurance and preparation of the training data are the basis for robust, trustworthy and generalisable modelling. During training stage, it is necessary to count on balanced datasets, where all the target classes are well represented for the classification problem (e.g., diseased vs control, classify cancer phenotypes, etc).

Reliability and reproducibility: In CAMEL we will count with different populations from different countries, which allows us to make different experiments to evaluate generalizability, reliability and reproducibility. A general model can be trained with data from all countries and then test the differential accuracy in global and at every country with new validation samples. It is also important to detect if some variable is impacting in the performance negatively, which will be done through statistical analysis.

R2 Ethical Requirements Check	
R2.1	Is the AI system certified for cybersecurity (e.g., the certification scheme created by the Cybersecurity Act in Europe) or is it compliant with specific security standards?
R2.2	Could the AI system have adversarial, critical or damaging effects (e.g., to human or societal safety) in case of risks or threats such as design or technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, inappropriate or malicious use?
R2.3	Could a low level of accuracy of the AI system have critical, adversarial or damaging consequences?
R2.4	Could the AI system cause critical, adversarial or damaging consequences (e.g., pertaining to human safety) in case of low reliability and/or reproducibility?
R2.5	Is the AI system using online continual learning?

Table 9 Technical Robustness and Safety Ethical Requirements

3.7.3 R3. Privacy and Data Governance

The AI models will be fully compliant with the GDPR and national legislation on relation to the protection of personal data. AI system(s) will be built in a way that embeds the principles of data minimisation and data protection by design and by default, as prescribed by the EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The Data Management Plan (T1.3, T2.3, T3.3) and the Continuous Monitoring of Ethical, legal and gender aspects (T1.4) of the CAMEL project will specifically consider how the systems

will comply to the applicable legislation carrying out Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) for each of the models. As previously mentioned, the models will be designed following privacy and security by design principles. To that end, appropriate technical and organisational measures will be set in place to safeguard the rights and freedoms of data subjects (e.g., appointment of data protection officer, anonymisation, pseudonymisation, encryption, aggregation). Strong security measures will be set in place to prevent data breaches and leakages and data will be acquired, stored and used in a manner which can be audited by humans.

R3 Ethical Requirements Check	
R3.1	The system processes data in line with the requirements for lawfulness, fairness and transparency set in the national and EU data protection legal framework and the reasonable expectations of the data subjects.
R3.2	Technical and organisational measures are in place to safeguard the rights of data subjects (through measures such as anonymisation, pseudonymisation, encryption, and aggregation).
R3.3	There are security measures in place to prevent data breaches and leakages (such as mechanisms for logging data access and data modification).

Table 10 Privacy and Governance Ethical Requirements

3.7.4 R4. Transparency

Traceability: The CAMEL AI lifecycle approach considers a set of tools and methodologies for consistent, traceable, and trustworthy development of AI models, which incorporate aspects such as:

- **Data Selection and Preparation Tools:** this prepares the training and validation datasets for AI modelling. VICOM also counts on a tabular data preparation tool developed within the H2020 project MIDAS.
- **Annotation Tools:** these are used to annotate data with expert ground truth and are typical for scenarios requiring clinical ground truth generation, such as image annotation by radiologists. Most of the data in CAMEL will be annotated through existing diagnoses, so there is no need for specific additional tools.
- **Model repository** with traceable versions of models and training data, with tools such as MLFlow and DVC.

Explainability: The described tools and methods will contribute to the explainability of the AI models. The AI driven decisions will be traced, analysed, benchmarked and explained to be understood to those directly and indirectly affected, mostly the clinicians and researchers and the patients subject of the pilot test, in order to allow for contesting of such decisions. Correlations will be assessed, analysed and reported as to why a model has generated a particular output or decision (and what combination of input factors contributed to that). If such correlations cannot be inferred, and can be considered as black boxes, alternative explainability measures will be considered (traceability, auditability, communication). To enhance explainability, CAMEL AI models will generate human-interpretable explanations for key decisions, allowing clinicians and researchers to verify outputs and challenge AI-generated insights when necessary.

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Communication: Communication of the AI systems’ capabilities, limitations and accuracy level will be at the core of the pilot test to be conducted with clinicians and researchers, by the means of a briefing about the trustworthiness of the prototype system. Thorough information about such limitations will also be provided on a plain language to the patients taking part in the pilot clinical study and included in the Informed Consent (IC) form, indicating the means of communication with the CAMEL interlocutors in terms of AI explainability and data protection.

R4 Ethical Requirements Check	
R4.1	The end-users are aware that they are interacting with an AI system.
R4.2	The purpose, capabilities, limitations, benefits and risks of the AI system and of the decisions conveyed are openly communicated to and understood by end-users and other stakeholders along with its possible consequences.
R4.3	People can audit, query, dispute, seek to change or object to AI or robotics activities (when applicable).
R4.4	The AI system enables traceability during its entire lifecycle, from initial design to post deployment evaluation and audit.
R4.5	The system offers details about how decisions are taken and on which reasons these were based (when relevant and possible).
R4.6	The system keeps records of the decisions made (when relevant).

Table 11 Transparency Ethical Requirements

3.7.5 R5. Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness

Avoidance of unfair bias: Bias occurs when the results of an algorithm cannot be generalized and these are skewed towards a particular population, variable or aspect of the input data. A problem with bias is that is typically not obvious and easy to detect. As bias is typical of human behaviour, it is natural that bias is also translated to the training data. However, it may also occur as part of the training process, where the algorithm favours some undesired characteristics / variables in the classification or pattern discovery. Unacceptable bias may skew results based on demographic aspects such as race, sex or income. Bias mitigation strategies such as data balancing will ensure equitable AI performance across diverse populations. However, some bias is acceptable if for example is used to deal with the differential biology or variability of populations. We will perform statistical (correlation) analysis of relevant variables to detect unacceptable biases. Bias in the algorithms’ programming will be prevented by implementing oversight processes to analyse and address the system’s purpose, constraints, requirements and decisions clearly and transparently. Additionally, AI models will be tested for differential accuracy across demographic groups to minimize disparities in cardiovascular risk assessment.

Accessibility and universal design: End-users will be clinicians and researchers, not the general population, so even if considering the accessibility, usability and acceptance when designing the interface and dashboards, such requirements will be lower than those when dealing with services aiming at a general population.

Stakeholder participation: The AI models will be designed, developed and tested following a co-creation process through a close and iterative interaction between clinicians, researchers and technology providers. Specifically, the engagement of patients will also be sought after mostly to assess the social and ethical acceptance and explainability of the proposed integrated CAMEL model, by the means of structured interviews and focus groups, to which end the expertise of Social Sciences and Humanities experts will be crucial.

R5 Ethical Requirements Check	
R5.1	The AI system is designed to avoid algorithmic bias, in input data, modelling and algorithm design.
R5.2	The AI system is designed to avoid historical and selection bias in data collection, representation and measurement bias in algorithmic training, aggregation and evaluation bias in modelling and automation bias in deployment.
R5.3	The system is designed so that it can be used different types of end-users with different abilities (whenever possible/relevant).
R5.4	The system does not have negative social impacts on relevant groups, including impacts other than those resulting from algorithmic bias or lack of universal accessibility.

Table 12 Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness Ethical Requirements

3.7.6 R6. Societal and Environmental Wellbeing

Environmental Wellbeing: No negative impact on the environment is expected from the CAMEL model. Moreover, incidentally, as the system relies on access to digital images and records, adopting such AI systems might further promote the digitalisation of all kinds of digital images and biology samples, reducing the use of material resources and storage needs in clinical premises. As a software, no life cycle assessment is considered from an environmental or circular economy perspective. However, AI models do have environmental implications, particularly due to the energy demands of training and running machine learning algorithms, as well as the water consumption required for cooling data centres. To mitigate these effects, CAMEL will explore energy-efficient AI training methods and adopt sustainability measures where possible.

Social impact: The social benefits of the AI systems for the general society cannot be argued as they aim to improve the health outcomes of the general population, mostly the current and future patients of RA. The CAMEL model is not aimed at its adoption by a general population. It can be considered as a professional tool that will enhance the decision-making of clinicians, so it is hardly expected to undermine or deteriorate the conception of health care providers or the social and personal relationships of the general population.

Impact on work and skills: CAMEL DSS will support clinicians in the diagnostics and treatment stages of the illness, following a Human in Command approach. The final decision will also fall under the clinician engaged in the pilot phase. Amongst the variables to be evaluated in the framework of the pilot, the time performance benefits in the health provision and the social acceptance of the tool by the clinicians vis a vis the impact of the AI tool in their work and skills will also be considered.

R6 Ethical Requirements Check	
R6.1	The AI system takes the welfare of all stakeholders into account and do not unduly or unfairly reduce/undermine their well-being.
R6.2	The AI system is mindful of principles of environmental sustainability, both regarding the system itself and the supply chain to which it connects (when relevant).
R6.3	The AI system does not have the potential to negatively impact the quality of communication, social interaction, information, democratic processes, and social relations (when relevant).
R6.4	The system does not reduce safety and integrity in the workplace and complies with the relevant health and safety and employment regulations.

Table 13 Societal and Environmental Ethical Requirements

3.7.7 R7. Accountability

As previously mentioned, CAMEL has put in place all necessary methods ensuring the auditability of the AI model, based upon the following tools:

- **Data Selection and Preparation Tools:** this prepares the training and validation datasets for AI modelling and can also be used to prepare a set of cases for validation. Within CAMEL, this will be implemented in data selection and verification. VICOM also counts on the GYDRA tabular data preparation tool developed within the H2020 Project MIDAS.
- **Annotation Tools:** these are used to annotate data with expert ground truth and are typical for scenarios requiring clinical ground truth generation, such as image annotation by radiologists. Most of the data in CAMEL will be annotated through existing diagnoses so additional annotation tools are not required.
- **Model repository and Lifecycle Management:** CAMEL will use the VICOM EREETA modelling framework for ML, alongside new AI lifecycle management tools developed within T3.10 to organize, track and monitor the AI models throughout their development and deployment. MLFlow and Data Version Control (DVC) will allow for traceability of training and validation datasets, as well as benchmarking different model architectures and hyperparameters to ensure robustness.
- **Benchmarking of Models:** These tools will be used to obtain performance statistics and are usually built into standard ML/DL modelling frameworks. The benchmarking will also be included in T3.10, supporting continuous evaluation of AI models.
- **Analysis Oriented to Ensuring Trustworthiness:** Statistical or mathematical analysis tools such as SPSS or R will be used to generate normalised reports assessing model accuracy, bias and reliability.
- **Explainability and Transparency Mechanisms:** To ensure accountability, explainable AI (XAI) approaches will be integrated into the system, providing visual outputs in the Clinical Decision Support System (CDSS, T10.3). This will allow clinicians and researchers to understand and challenge AI-generated predictions when necessary.

These tools will ensure:

- Detection and mitigation of ethically and socially undesirable effects (e.g., bias, lack of transparency, or incorrect AI predictions).
- Persistent human oversight and control over the decision cycles and operation.

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- Procedures and communication channels for end-users, data subjects and other third parties to report complaints, ethical concerns, or adverse events and how these will be evaluated, addressed and communicated back to the concerned parties.
- The AI models will have specific risk assessment procedures and mitigation measures during design, testing and deployment.

R7 Ethical Requirements Check	
R7.1	The AI system details how potential ethically and socially undesirable effects will be detected, stopped, and prevented from reoccurring.
R7.2	The AI system allows for human oversight during the entire life cycle of the project regarding their decision cycles and operation (when relevant).

Table 14 Accountability Ethical Requirements

3.8 Data Management Principles

Data plays a crucial role in CAMEL, considering the overall approach of the project mirroring the topic where it was funded, titled [HORIZON-HLTH-2024-STAYHLTH-01-05-two-stage](#) - Personalised prevention of non-communicable diseases - addressing areas of unmet needs using multiple data sources.

As referred in section 1.1, the goal of CAMEL is to develop and validate a novel stratified approach for personalised prevention in women around the menopause transition (40-60 years), enabled by a variety of diagnostic technologies (molecular biomarkers, imaging, etc.) and digital data sources (EHR, cohorts, registries, biobanks, etc.) leveraging multiple-data sources. CAMEL will investigate different approaches for data integration and computational modelling, developing state-of-the-art approaches in AI and personalised risk prediction. The leverage of multiple data sources is thus at the core of the project methodology and approach. A CAMEL Data Management Plan (D1.2) has been produced that should be read in conjunction with this Ethics and Gender Guidelines document. It outlines the data to be collected, processed and re-used, as well as measures taken to ensure that data management adheres to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). It also details the management of other research outputs, the overarching ethical and security principles and procedures implemented to ensure compliance with applicable regulations, including the GDPR⁷⁷ regulation, the AI Act (AIA)⁷⁸ and the European Health Data Spaces (EHDS)⁷⁹ Regulation.

77 REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

78 REGULATION (EU) 2024/1689 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008,

(EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act)

79 REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the European Health Data Space and amending Directive 2011/24/EU and Regulation (EU) 2024/2847

4. Gender Guidelines

4.1 Introduction

Integrating sex and gender analysis into research and innovation contributes to better science by improving the quality of new knowledge, and ensures maximum impact by enhancing the societal relevance of research evidence and outputs, technologies and services. Sex and gender analysis in each and all phases of the research process requires an interdisciplinary collaborative approach to understanding diversity and to knowledge sharing. Understanding sex-based and gender-based difference and sensitivity is vital for accurate research prediction and response and appreciation of sex-based difference may be needed for the development of new tools and methods to generate relevant sex-disaggregated data for sex specific diseases and conditions⁸⁰. This is important in the field of biomedical research and healthcare because of the sex specific and gender-based differences in CVD presentation and the risks for cardiovascular disease. Researchers should be equipped with the necessary skills to apply sex and gender analysis, but first, preliminary understanding of the relevant key terms is necessary.

4.2 Menopause, Sex and Gender

Menopause is caused by the loss of ovarian follicular function and a decline in circulating blood oestrogen levels, and for most individuals, is experienced between the ages of 45 and 55 years as a natural part of biological ageing, or occasionally earlier, as a consequence of surgical or medical procedure. Perimenopause refers to the period from when signs are first observed and ends one year after the final menstrual period. Perimenopause can last several years and can affect physical, emotional, mental and social well-being⁸¹. While it is true that menopause is experienced predominantly by women, it is also true that menopause may be experienced by transgender men and by individuals who are non-binary⁸². The terms 'transgender' and 'non-binary' refer to gender, and 'gender' is a social construct. Menopause may also be experienced by individuals who are intersex; this is a biological construct. Understanding of gender, sex and associated terms is essential to avoid sex and gender bias in research, and the subsequent alienation and exclusion of those who may be affected by menopause. There are challenges for researchers who should understand that sex and gender are separate concepts, but also that they are inherently interconnected, interrelated and may be inseparable. As science develops, definitions of sex and gender evolve, other challenges may be that researchers experience difficulties in separating biological from social constructs⁸³. A proactive approach to addressing gender bias ameliorates the risk of knowledge deficit.

80 Peters SAE, Woodward M. A roadmap for sex- and gender-disaggregated health research. *BMC Med.* 2023 Sep 13;21(1):354. doi: 10.1186/s12916-023-03060-w. PMID: 37704983; PMCID: PMC10500779.

81 WHO (2024) Menopause <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/menopause>

Merone L, Tsey K, Russell D, Nagle C. Sex Inequalities in Medical Research: A Systematic Scoping Review of the Literature. *Women's Health Rep (New Rochelle)*. 2022 Jan 31;3(1):49-59. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35136877/>

82 NICE (2022) National Institute For Health And Care Excellence Nice Guidelines Equality Impact Assessment Menopause (update) <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng23/update/ng23-update-1/documents/801>

83 Kaufman MR, Eschliman EL, Karver TS. Differentiating sex and gender in health research to achieve gender equity. *Bull World Health Organ.* 2023 Oct 1;101(10):666-671. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37772198/>

4.3 Understanding Sex

In humans, 'sex' refers to the biological attributes of genetics, anatomy and physiology that distinguish male, female and intersex. Intersex conditions may be defined as variations or combinations of what are considered XY male-typical and XX female-typical chromosomal, gonadal and genital characteristics⁸⁴ (European Commission 2020, p12-13).

4.4 Understanding Gender

Gender is a multidimensional social construct that is culturally and historically specific and is subject to change. Gender refers to sociocultural norms, identities and relations that shape feminine and masculine behaviours. Gender attitudes and behaviours are complex and change over time and place. Gender is distinct from sex.

4.5 Understanding Intersectionality

Gender and sex can combine or intersect with other social categories, such as age, disability, socioeconomic status, sexual orientation and ethnic origin to exacerbate disparity or to shape a person's or group's experiences and/or opportunities. This can lead to inequality, or discrimination, or bias.

4.6 Sex and Gender Bias in Research

Sex and gender biases may occur at researcher, provider, patient, and societal levels. Bias can contribute to differences in cardiovascular disease (CVD) recognition and treatment, outcome disparities between sexes and genders, and underestimation of the risk of cardiac events in females compared with males⁸⁵. Of relevance, it is noteworthy that CVD risk assessment models do not duly take into consideration female or women-specific risk factors⁸⁶.

4.6.1 Sex Bias in Research

Sex bias in research can result in prejudice that favours one sex over another and may manifest potentially in more resources directed at diseases that typically affect more males than females. Sex bias may also result in less knowledge about the conditions and related treatment of diseases that are typically associated with greater female prevalence⁸⁷. Historical

84 European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. (2020). Gendered Innovations 2: How Inclusive Analysis Contributes to Research and Innovation: Policy Review. Publications Office <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/316197>

85 Kim I, Field TS, Wan D, Humphries K, Sedlak T. Sex and Gender Bias as a Mechanistic Determinant of Cardiovascular Disease Outcomes. *Can J Cardiol*. 2022 Dec;38(12). <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36116747/>

86 Al Hamid A, Beckett R, Wilson M, et al. (February 15, 2024) Gender Bias in Diagnosis, Prevention, and Treatment of Cardiovascular Diseases: A Systematic Review. *Cureus* 16(2): e54264. DOI 10.7759/cureus.54264

87 Sullivan K, Doumouras BS, Santema BT, et al. Sex-specific differences in heart failure: pathophysiology, risk factors, management, and outcomes. *Can J Cardiol* 2021;37:560-71. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0828282X2031196X>

and current focus on males in medical research has led to gaps in understanding the impact of conditions on females (Merone et al 2022)⁸⁸.

4.6.2 Gender Bias in Research

Gender bias refers to any systematic difference in practices or beliefs that favour one gender over another. The results of a systematic review by Al Hamid et al (2024) indicate the presence of gender bias against women in relation to CVD diagnosis, prevention, and treatment, such that women are likely to receive fewer diagnostic tests, are less likely to be invited to participate in research and are less likely to be offered treatment that is deemed aggressive.

4.7 Sex and Gender Analysis in Research Training

All CAMEL researchers will undertake an ‘Integrating Sex and Gender Analysis in Research’ training programme, comprising units of learning designated to each phase of the research process. All modules/units should be completed prior to M06 and researchers will sign a declaration stating their completion of training. Should any new researcher join the CAMEL team over the course of the project, they will also complete this training as part of the on-boarding process.

On completion, participants will:

- Understand the significance, relevance and meaning of sex and gender analysis in research
- Grasp key determinants and principles of sex and gender analysis in research
- Identify and offset the potential risks of sex and gender bias prompted by the absence of sex and gender analysis

Module/Unit	Title
1.	Introduction: Why gender and sex analysis matters; key concepts and operational definitions
2.	Principles of analysing sex and gender with reference to identifying the problem/research question
3.	Principles of analysing sex and gender with reference to the research design and approach/methodology
4.	Principles of analysing sex and gender with reference to collecting data
5.	Principles of analysing sex and gender with reference to analysing data

⁸⁸ Merone L, Tsey K, Russell D, Nagle C. Sex Inequalities in Medical Research: A Systematic Scoping Review of the Literature. *Womens Health Rep (New Rochelle)*. 2022 Jan 31;3(1):49-59. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35136877/>

6.	Principles of analysing sex and gender with reference to reporting and dissemination
7.	Summary and evaluation

Table 15 Sex and Gender Training Outline and Goals

4.8 Overall Governance

TCD, as a member of the GLED Committee will advise according to best practice for sex and gender dimensions in CAMEL research activities, primarily in the design of the CAMEL studies. Coordination of completion of tasks will be monitored by project team leaders. CAMEL researchers will complete the gender and sex training programme and sign a declaration of completion (prepared by VICOM) to be sent to VICOM by M06 (June). Each research team is responsible for their team's compliance with the educational training offered. Once the declaration of completion of training has been signed, the researcher is accountable for adhering to best practice during the course of the research.

4.9 Resources

The programme of Sex and Gender Analysis in Research Training is informed by resources, guidelines and material from the following: ACT (<https://act-on-gender.eu/>)⁸⁹ a Horizon 2020 project that seeks to advance gender equality in universities, research centres and research funding organisations by establishing communities of practice, and additional publications from the European Commission and European Institute for Gender Equality.

⁸⁹ Müller, Jörg, Pollitzer, Elizabeth. (2021, July). ACT on Integrating Sex and Gender Analysis in Research & Innovation. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5137588>

5. Gender, Legal, Ethical and Data Governance

Data management and ethical management issues are closely linked. Both activities are considered within Work Package 1, in Task 1.3 and Task 1.4 and in subsequent tasks in Work Packages 2 and 3. From the outset of the CAMEL project, the **Gender, Legal, Ethics & Data (GLED) Committee** has significantly contributed to the definition and update of the Data Management Plan (D1.2) and of these Ethics and Gender Guidelines (D1.3), and they will have a central role in the monitoring of compliance of the GLED guidelines.

5.1 The GLED Committee

A Gender, Legal, Ethics & Data (GLED) Committee has been set-up with the participation of VICOM (responsible for the definition and update of the DMP), DCU (ethical expert and GLED Chair), TLX (legal expert), TCD (gender expert) and clinical partners (main data providers) with the goals of ensuring the compliance of the planned research to the highest legal and ethical standards, including the GDPR, as well as integrity, inclusivity, and social responsibility principles.

The Committee is chaired by DCU and will implement activities related to the coordination and management of ethical and safety issues applicable to the project. It also comprises legal issues, led by TLX, ensuring the project's compliance with GDPR and applicable regulations relating to AI, health, and data sharing. Specific activities will ensure the implementation of appropriate data protection and safety measures to protect the privacy of the CAMEL human participants, including anonymisation of personal data relating to health. An evaluation of the ethical feasibility of the proposed solutions will also be performed, alongside an analysis on any potential risks or ethical concerns. This process will also provide support to technical partners in handling sensitive aspects of research activities, ensuring that the design of study protocols and research procedures strictly adhere to the project's ethical code of conduct. Thus, the GLED will support in the definition of the co-design exercises for specifications and requirements elicitation (WP4) and the clinical studies protocols (WP11-WP13).

5.2 GLED / TMT Monitoring and Reporting

The review of the gender, legal, ethical, and data aspects related to CAMEL research activities will be carried out by GLED.

- Each partner has identified a key point of contact who is a member of the GLED. These individuals are responsible for documenting gender, legal, ethical, and/or data issues as they arise. They are also responsible for bringing these issues to the attention of the GLED Committee at the next meeting (scheduled every two weeks). A standing item has been added to the agenda of the fortnightly GLED Committee meetings to monitor new and open GLED issues.
- The Chair of the GLED Committee (DCU) will summarise GLED issues at the following TMT meeting. These are also held fortnightly on alternate weeks.
- GLED issues will also be monitored on a 6-monthly basis as part of CAMEL consortium meetings.

In extraordinary circumstances (i.e. if an urgent and/or high impact issue arises), these will be brought directly to the attention of the GLED Chair. If necessary, an extraordinary GLED

meeting will be convened to discuss the issue and determine the appropriate resolution. The outcome of this meeting will be communicated to all relevant partners by the GLED Chair.

All issues and the steps involved in their resolution will be tracked by the GLED Committee.

5.3 Periodic Reporting of GLED compliance

A review of the gender, legal, ethical, and data aspects related to CAMEL research activities will be carried out by the GLED as part of the periodic reporting for CAMEL (every 20 months) and at the end of each CAMEL study. An online form focused on reporting on compliance with ethical, legal and gender standards for conducting research will be completed by each partner. Responses will be gathered and collated by the GLED chair for inclusion in the CAMEL periodic report.

Ethical, Legal and Gender Compliance Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are you familiar with the ethical, legal and gender guidelines of the CAMEL project? • Are you familiar with the CAMEL Data Management Plan?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you comply with the following CAMEL standards and guidelines (tick all that apply)? Ethical, Legal, Gender, Data
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you have any (new or old) ethical documentation regarding the CAMEL clinical studies that has not yet been forwarded to DCU? Please describe. • Are you submitting any (new or old) ethical documentation with this report? Please describe. <p><i>Please note: copies of all approved and unapproved protocols from any local ethical committees, ethical boards, administrations and legal bodies related to ethics must be forwarded to the GLED Chair for the purpose of official documentation.</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have you conducted any extraordinary data collection or study not described in the CAMEL DoA for any reason? Please describe and include rationale/justification.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What GLED issues have you (researcher) experienced (since your last periodic report)?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What GLED issues have been experienced by research participants (since the last periodic report)?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have any previously reported GLED issues been resolved since the last periodic report? Please name them and explain how they were resolved.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there any questions or comments that you would like to raise regarding GLED processes, issues and/or this form?

Table 16 Accountability Ethical Requirements

Additionally, all partners have identified a Data Manager who will oversee the CAMEL data collection and protection in their organisations. This information is listed in section 5 of the CAMEL DMP (D1.2).

6. Allocation of resources

CAMEL has dedicated Task T1.4 in WP1 to the development of ethics and gender guidelines. All partners have thus time efforts allocated to take part in the gender, legal, ethical and data management of the project. Table 17 lists the staff allocated by each partner to that end:

Nº	Short name	GLED Member	Name	Email
1	VICOM	Members	Iván Macía, Cristina Martín, Ion Gorriti, Ines Hanrion	imacia@vicomtech.org cmartin@vicomtech.org igorriti@vicomtech.org ihanrion@vicomtech.org
2	A3Z	Members	Miguel Ángel Campanero, Inés Suárez	macampanero@a3zadvanced.com , gestioncalidad7@a3zadvanced.com
3	KER	Clinical Member	Kelly Rocio Chacon	krchacon@keralty.com
4	BK	Member	Catalina Martínez	catalina.martinez@keralty.com
5	PARTICLE	Member	Bárbara Guerra	barbara@particle-summary.pt
6	IBREVE	Member	Flavia Wahl	wahl@ibreve.com
7	MAG	Clinical Member	Marta Curman	marta.curman@magdalena.hr
8	MEGI	Member	Ines Knežević	ines@megi.ai
9	NKUA	Clinical Member	Alexandros Nakis	alexandrosnakis@icloud.com
10	SAS	Clinical Member	Francisco Jose Nuñez, Miguel Giráldez	fjose.nunez@juntadeandalucia.es miguel.giraldez@juntadeandalucia.es
11	FISEVI	Members	Francisco Jose Nuñez, Miguel Giráldez	fjose.nunez@juntadeandalucia.es miguel.giraldez@juntadeandalucia.es
12	SIT	Member	Giulia Onorati	giulia.onorati@socialit.it
13	TCD	Sex and Gender	Vivienne Brady	bradyvi@tcd.ie

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14	TREE		Rebeca García Betances, Tatiana Silva	rebeca.garcia@treetk.com tatiana.silva@treetk.com
15	VULSK	Clinical Member	Indre Paulauskaite	Indre.Paulauskaite@santa.lt
16	CIC	Member	Nieves Embade	nembade@cicbiogune.es
17	ASC	Member	Anna García Elias	agarciae@cetir.es
18	HRI	Member	Robert Kelly	robert@heartrhythmireland.com
19	DCU	Chair (Ethics)	Louise Hopper	louise.hopper@dcu.ie
20	TAU	Member	Reijo Laaksonen	reijo.laaksonen@tuni.fi
21	ULMA	Member	Erik Isusquiza	eisusquiza@ulma.com
22	BGU	Member	Tuval Shahrar	yshahrar01@gmail.com
23	SNSI	Member	Joseph Muallem	josephmuallem.sns@gmail.com
24	BIO	Lead member from PHC	Irene Alonso Sampedro	Irene.alonsosampedro@bio-gipuzkoa.eus
		Backup member from PHC	Kalliopi Vrotsou	Kalliopi.Vrotsoux@osakidetza.eus
		Lead member from ISU	Asma Shaheen	Asma.shaheenxx@bio-gipuzkoa.eus
25	TLX	Legal Member	Magdalena Gad-Nowak	magdalena.gad@timelex.eu

Table 17 GLED Members and Ethics Contacts in other CAMEL partners

Each partner will have to respect and follow the guidelines set out in this report. VICOM, as Project Coordinator and DCU as Chair of the GLED Committee, with the support of GLED members will have the responsibility to ensure that all CAMEL research is conducted in compliance with agreed principles and measures.

To that end, the GLED Committee will be the main body providing guidance to the whole of the consortium in the implementation, monitoring and potential update of the Ethics and Gender Guidelines, ensuring compliance to design of the ethical, gender, legal and privacy regulations and guidelines. Thus, when partners need assistance with ethics- or gender-

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related questions, members of the GLED, mostly DCU, TCD, TLCX and VICOM will be available to discuss and provide guidance.

Besides time efforts, a number of eligible direct costs linked to the implementation of the Ethics and Gender guidelines are also considered:

- Fees linked to the management of approval of clinical studies by Ethics Committees.
- Publication fees for scientific publications only when publishing in full open access venues.

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PERSONALISED PREVENTION STRATEGIES TARGETING MENOPAUSAL WOMEN**

7. Conclusions

The CAMEL project's "Ethics and Gender Guidelines" provides a comprehensive framework for navigating the complex legal, ethical, and gender-related considerations inherent in cardiovascular disease research targeting menopausal women. By adhering to these guidelines, the CAMEL consortium aims to ensure the project's activities are conducted responsibly, ethically, and in compliance with relevant regulations. The document establishes a foundation for promoting trustworthy AI, protecting participant data, and addressing gender biases in research. The ongoing monitoring and reporting of GLED issues by the dedicated GLED committee will be crucial for the project's success and its contribution to improving cardiovascular health outcomes for women.